

**A REVIEW OF THE SYSTEMATIC STUDY ON THE
EXACT STATIC SYMMETRIC SOLUTIONS OF
EINSTEIN FIELD EQUATIONS**

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CANDIDATE'S DECLARATION

I hereby, declare that the work presented in the dissertation entitled “**A REVIEW OF THE SYSTEMATIC STUDY ON THE EXACT STATIC SYMMETRIC SOLUTIONS OF EINSTEIN FIELD EQUATIONS**” for partial fulfillment of the requirement for the degree of Master of Science in Mathematics and submitted to the Department of Mathematics at Pondicherry University, is an authentic record of my own work carried out during the period from January 2024 to June 2024 under the supervision of **Dr. RAJESWARI SESHADRI**.

The matter presented in this thesis has not been submitted elsewhere, in part or fully, to any other University or Institute for the award of any other degree.

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ABSTRACT

Einstein field equations (EFEs) is one of the most celebrated Equation over a Century ever since Einstein first introduced them in 1915 as a Tensor Equation. These are a set of ten nonlinear partial differential Equations derived from General Theory of Relativity, which basically describe the interaction of Gravitation, where Einstein explained that measure of space time Curvature is the source of gravity.

This dissertation presents a comprehensive review of the exact static symmetric solutions of Einstein's field equations that describes how matter and energy shape the curvature of space-time. The investigation begins with an in-depth analysis of the Schwarzschild metric and its consequential extensions, incorporating seminal works by Droste and Moffat. The study provides detailed examinations of metric solutions across various coordinate systems, viz. Gullstrand-Painlevé, Eddington-Finkelstein, Lemaître, and Kruskal-Szekere etc. highlighting their profound physical interpretations and theoretical applications. The research extends to sophisticated geometrical constructs, such as the Einstein-Rosen Bridge and Synge's tetrad formalism, illustrating their significant implications for the theoretical landscape. Through rigorous mathematical scrutiny, the thesis elucidates the pivotal role these exact solutions play in our understanding of the universe's geometric structure.

Furthermore, the thesis investigates axially symmetric solutions, delving into metrics such as Weyl, Levi-Civita, Lewis, Papapetrou, Kerr, Tomimatsu-Sato, and among others. The incorporation of modern theoretical approaches, including spheroidal space-time metrics, toroidal space-time, and concepts of quasi-hyperbolicity, adds substantial depth to the present study. This comprehensive analysis not only significantly contributes to the domain of theoretical physics but also serves as an indispensable resource for future scholarly inquiries. The findings elevate our comprehension of static symmetric solutions and lay a robust groundwork for investigating more complex and dynamic solutions within the General Relativity framework. This dissertation thus stands as a crucial beacon for advancing our grasp of the cosmos through the lens of mathematical precision and theoretical innovation.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

The advent of the general theory of relativity by [Einstein \[1915\]](#) marked a transformative era in our understanding of gravitation, space, and time. This groundbreaking theory superseded Newtonian mechanics by providing a more comprehensive framework that encapsulates the intricate relationship between matter and the curvature of spacetime. The core of Einstein's theory is encapsulated in the Einstein field equations, a set of ten interrelated differential equations that describe how matter and energy in the universe influence the curvature of spacetime. These equations have not only deepened our comprehension of the universe but also predicted phenomena that were later confirmed by observation, such as the bending of light by gravity and the existence of black holes.

Historically, the intellectual odyssey that culminated in the formulation of the Einstein field equations was marked by profound theoretical advancements and intense scientific scrutiny. The journey began with Einstein's special theory of relativity in 1905, which elegantly unified the laws of mechanics with Maxwell's electromagnetism, establishing the constancy of the speed of light and the relativistic effects of time dilation and length contraction. However, the special theory of relativity was restricted to inertial frames and failed to incorporate gravitational phenomena. It was the subsequent realization that gravitation could be interpreted as the curvature of spacetime, influenced by mass and energy, that led to the general theory of relativity—a framework capable of describing gravitational interactions in any reference frame.

The Einstein field equations, typically expressed as $G_{mn} + \Lambda g_{mn} = \frac{8\pi G}{c^4} T_{mn}$, where G_{mn} is the Einstein tensor describing the curvature of spacetime, Λ is the cosmological constant, g_{mn} is the metric tensor defining the geometry of spacetime, T_{mn} is the stress-energy tensor representing matter and energy, G is the gravitational constant, and c is the speed of light, succinctly encapsulate the dynamic interplay between spacetime and matter. Despite their seemingly compact form, these equations are rich in content and have profound implications for our understanding of

the universe.

The solutions to the Einstein field equations have played a crucial role in advancing our knowledge of astrophysical phenomena. The first exact solution, discovered by [Schwarzschild \[1916\]](#), describes the spacetime geometry surrounding a non-rotating, spherically symmetric mass. This Schwarzschild solution was instrumental in developing the concept of black holes and predicting the existence of event horizons. Schwarzschild's work demonstrated that under certain conditions, the gravitational collapse of a massive star could lead to a singularity, a point where the curvature of spacetime becomes infinite.

Further advancements came with the exploration of more complex and realistic scenarios. [Kerr \[1963\]](#) found an exact solution for a rotating black hole, now known as the *Kerr metric*, which revealed the possibility of *rotating event horizons and ergospheres*. This solution opened new avenues in the study of astrophysical black holes, suggesting that most celestial bodies with significant mass would likely be rotating, thus influencing the surrounding spacetime in more intricate ways than previously understood.

The study of Einstein's field equations has also led to the discovery of numerous fascinating geometrical constructs and theoretical insights. For instance, the Einstein-Rosen bridge, or wormhole, proposed by [Einstein and Rosen \[1935\]](#), provides a hypothetical connection between distant regions of spacetime, offering intriguing possibilities for faster-than-light travel and connections between different universes. Similarly, the development of tetrad formalism by [Synge \[1950\]](#) has provided powerful mathematical tools for analyzing the structure of spacetime.

Moreover, the study of axially symmetric solutions has yielded significant results. Metrics such as the [Weyl \[1917\]](#), [Levi-Civita \[1917\]](#), [Lewis \[1932\]](#), [Papapetrou \[1953\]](#), Kerr and [Tomimatsu and Sato \[1972\]](#) metrics have been pivotal in understanding systems with rotational symmetry. These solutions have been instrumental in the theoretical modeling of astrophysical objects like rotating stars, black holes, and galaxies.

In addition to these classic solutions, modern theoretical physics has extended Einstein's equations to incorporate quantum effects and higher-dimensional spacetimes. The development of spheroidal space-time metrics, toroidal spacetimes, and quasi-hyperbolicity has expanded the scope of general relativity, integrating it with quantum mechanics and string theory. These advancements have opened new frontiers in our understanding of the fundamental nature of the universe, including the behavior of spacetime at microscopic scales and the potential existence of extra dimensions.

This thesis embarks on an exhaustive exploration of the historical development and mathematical intricacies of the Einstein field equations, from their inception

to their contemporary applications and implications. By delving into the key milestones, significant solutions, and profound impact of these equations on theoretical physics, we aim to provide a comprehensive understanding of how Einstein's visionary equations have reshaped our view of the cosmos. Through meticulous analysis and detailed exposition, this work seeks to honor the intellectual legacy of Einstein and the ongoing quest for knowledge that continues to drive the field of general relativity and cosmology. This comprehensive review not only celebrates the intellectual triumph of Einstein and his successors but also serves as a foundational resource for future research in the ever-evolving landscape of theoretical physics.

Chapter 2

Spherically Symmetric Solutions

2.1 Schwarzschild Metric

2.1.1 Metric solutions by Droste

The breakthrough of the theory of relativity contexting in the paper communicated by [Einstein \[1915\]](#), succeeded in framing equations which are covariant for all possible transformations. From the set of new equations, [Droste \[1917\]](#) calculated the field of a single centre at rest, for which he presented the metric solutions.

For a centre that is at rest and symmetrical in all directions, it may be easily seen that

$$ds^2 = w^2 dt^2 - dr^2 - v^2(d\theta^2 + \sin^2 \theta d\phi^2), \quad (2.1.1)$$

where w and v only depending on r , and (θ, ϕ) representing polar coordinates. Then the Einstein tensor one can find

$$G_{tr} = \frac{-4w''}{w}, \quad G_{\theta r} = G_{\phi r} = \frac{-4v''}{v}, \quad G_{t\phi} = G_{t\theta} = \frac{-4v'w'}{vw}, \quad G_{\theta\phi} = \frac{4}{v^2} - \frac{4v'^2}{v^2}. \quad (2.1.2)$$

Here accents stand for differentiation with respect to r in these equations.

The field equations for which the metric solution (2.1.1) is valid are

$$2vv'' + v'^2 = 1 \quad (2.1.3)$$

and

$$vw'' + v'w' + wv'' = 0. \quad (2.1.4)$$

To solve (2.1.4), introducing the new quantity x instead of r such that on taking account of (2.1.3), the equation (2.1.4) becomes

$$(1 - x^2) \frac{d^2w}{dx^2} - 2x \frac{dw}{dx} + 2w = 0. \quad (2.1.5)$$

Since w is finite if $v' = 1$ (for $r = \infty$), then w must be equal to x as it satisfies the differential equation (2.1.5).

The introduction of x in (2.1.3) gives the solution

$$v = \frac{\alpha}{1 - x^2}, \quad (2.1.6)$$

where α is an integration constant. Differentiating (2.1.6) with respect to r and then assuming v' being equal to x , we obtain

$$dr = \frac{2\alpha dx}{(1 - x^2)^2}. \quad (2.1.7)$$

So the metric (2.1.1) becomes

$$ds^2 = x^2 dt^2 - \frac{4\alpha^2}{(1 - x^2)^4} dx^2 - \frac{\alpha^2}{(1 - x^2)^2} (d\theta^2 + \sin^2 \theta d\phi^2). \quad (2.1.8)$$

Lastly, if we put $1 - x^2 = \frac{\alpha}{R}$ in (2.1.8), we obtain

$$ds^2 = \left(1 - \frac{\alpha}{R}\right) dt^2 - \left(1 - \frac{\alpha}{R}\right)^{-1} dR^2 - R^2 (d\theta^2 + \sin^2 \theta d\phi^2). \quad (2.1.9)$$

The point (R, θ, ϕ) is observed to lie at a distance from the point, where the radius intersects the sphere $R = \alpha$. Also, a moving particle outside sphere $R = \alpha$ can never pass that sphere.

Now, solving the equations of motion of a particle in the field one can obtain the acceleration in case of a particle at rest ($\frac{dR}{dt} = 0$) which is directed towards the centre as

$$\frac{d^2\phi}{dt^2} = 0, \quad \frac{d^2R}{dt^2} = \frac{-\alpha}{2R^2} \left(1 - \frac{\alpha}{R}\right). \quad (2.1.10)$$

This implies that R has its greatest value (at rest) at the distance $R = \frac{3}{2}\alpha$ from the centre.

Now, consider the classification for the spherically symmetric line element (studied by Schwarzschild [1916], Droste [1917]) established by Eisenstaedt [1982].

If one takes the radial transformation

$$R = \bar{r} + \alpha \quad (2.1.11)$$

then the line element (2.1.9) becomes

$$ds^2 = \left(1 + \frac{\alpha}{\bar{r}}\right)^{-1} dt^2 - \left(1 + \frac{\alpha}{\bar{r}}\right) d\bar{r}^2 - (\bar{r} + \alpha)^2 (d\theta^2 + \sin^2 \theta d\phi^2). \quad (2.1.12)$$

Again setting the transformation of radial co-ordinate defined in (2.1.11) to a new temporal co-ordinate, $\bar{r} = -\tau$, one gets the line element

$$ds^2 = \left(\frac{\alpha - \tau}{\tau}\right) d\tau^2 - \left(\frac{\tau}{\alpha - \tau}\right) dt^2 - (\alpha - \tau)^2 (d\theta^2 + \sin^2 \theta d\phi^2). \quad (2.1.13)$$

2.1.2 Metric solutions by Moffat

Introducing the real and imaginary parts, Moffat [1957] defined the complex symmetric tensor $g_{\mu\nu}$ as

$$g_{\mu\nu} = \hat{g}_{\mu\nu} + g_{\mu\nu}^*, \quad (2.1.14)$$

where $\hat{}$ and $\star$ denote real and imaginary quantities, respectively. Then the structures of the gravitational fields can be determined by the complex symmetric tensor $g_{\mu\nu}$.

Considering $\hat{\Gamma}_{\mu\nu}^\lambda$, a real symmetrical affine field and $\Gamma_{\mu\nu}^{\star\lambda}$, an imaginary symmetrical tensor field, the notion of a complex symmetric affine connexion $\Gamma_{\mu\nu}^\lambda$ with space-time, satisfying the transformation law in Riemannian geometry, one writes

$$\Gamma_{\mu\nu}^\lambda = \hat{\Gamma}_{\mu\nu}^\lambda + \Gamma_{\mu\nu}^{\star\lambda}. \quad (2.1.15)$$

Taking into consideration of covariant differentiation defined by Moffat [1957], one can obtain field equations as

$$R_{\mu\nu} = -\frac{\partial\Gamma_{\mu\nu}^\lambda}{\partial x_\lambda} + \frac{\partial\Gamma_{\mu\lambda}^\lambda}{\partial x_\nu} + \Gamma_{\rho\nu}^\lambda\Gamma_{\mu\lambda}^\rho - \Gamma_{\mu\nu}^\lambda\Gamma_{\lambda\rho}^\rho. \quad (2.1.16)$$

For empty static homogeneous space-time, in which matter is absent, the field equations are

$$R_{\mu\nu} = 0. \quad (2.1.17)$$

Let us choose polar co-ordinates

$$x_1 = r, \quad x_2 = \theta, \quad x_3 = \phi, \quad x_4 = t,$$

such that the line element determining the gravitational field and metric of space-time is then assumed to be of the spherically symmetric form

$$ds^2 = -\eta dr^2 - r^2(d\theta^2 + \sin^2\theta d\phi^2) + \alpha dt^2, \quad (2.1.18)$$

where the real η and α are functions of r only. Here the metric properties of space-time are described by the real quadratic form

$$ds^2 = \hat{g}_{\mu\nu} dx_\mu dx_\nu. \quad (2.1.19)$$

In accordance with (2.1.18) the complex fundamental tensor $g_{\mu\nu}$, one determines

$$\begin{aligned} g_{11} &= -\mu(r) = -(\eta + i\xi) = -e^\lambda, \\ g_{22} &= g_{22}^* = -r^2, \\ g_{33} &= g_{33}^* = -r^2 \sin^2\theta, \\ g_{00} &= \gamma(r) = (\alpha + i\beta) = e^\nu, \end{aligned} \quad (2.1.20)$$

and

$$g_{\mu\nu} = 0 \quad \text{if} \quad \mu \neq \nu,$$

where the real η, ξ, α, β and the complex $\mu, \gamma, \lambda, \nu$ are functions of r only. Then one can find the determinant of g as

$$-g = e^{\lambda+\nu} r^4 \sin^2 \theta. \quad (2.1.21)$$

Further calculating the components of complex symmetric connexion $\Gamma_{\mu\nu}^\lambda$, one can derive the field equations considering (2.1.20) as

$$R_{11} = \frac{\nu''}{2} - \frac{\lambda' \nu'}{4} + \frac{\nu'^2}{4} - \frac{\lambda'}{r} = 0, \quad (2.1.22)$$

$$R_{22} = e^{-\lambda} \left(1 + \frac{1}{2} r (\nu' - \lambda') \right) - 1 = 0, \quad (2.1.23)$$

$$R_{33} = \sin^2 \theta e^{-\lambda} \left(1 + \frac{1}{2} r (\nu' - \lambda') \right) - \sin^2 \theta = 0, \quad (2.1.24)$$

$$R_{00} = e^{\nu-\lambda} \left(\frac{-\nu''}{2} + \frac{\lambda' \nu'}{4} - \frac{\nu'^2}{4} - \frac{\nu'}{r} \right) = 0. \quad (2.1.25)$$

From the equations (2.1.22) and (2.1.25), we have

$$\lambda' = -\nu'. \quad (2.1.26)$$

But the boundary conditions for the sphere states that as $r \rightarrow \infty$, $\alpha \rightarrow 1$, $\eta \rightarrow 0$, $\beta \rightarrow 0$ and $\xi \rightarrow 0$. So (2.1.26) reduces to

$$\lambda = -\nu. \quad (2.1.27)$$

Since $\sin^2 \theta R_{22} = R_{33}$, then the equation (2.1.23) yields

$$e^\nu (1 + r\nu') = 1. \quad (2.1.28)$$

As $e^\nu = \gamma$ from (2.1.20), one obtains

$$\gamma + r\gamma' = 1. \quad (2.1.29)$$

Separating real and imaginary parts, one writes

$$\alpha + r\alpha' = 1, \quad \beta + r\beta' = 0. \quad (2.1.30)$$

If we assume that $\beta = 0$ is one solution and then integrating (2.1.30) for α only, we get

$$\alpha = 1 - \frac{2m}{r}, \quad (2.1.31)$$

where $2m$ is real constant of integration which can be identified as the mass. From (2.1.27) we have

$$e^{-\nu} = \gamma^{-1} = e^\lambda = \eta + i\xi. \quad (2.1.32)$$

But for $\beta = 0$,

$$\gamma^{-1} = \alpha^{-1} = \eta = \left(1 - \frac{2m}{r} \right)^{-1}. \quad (2.1.33)$$

Then the substitution into (2.1.18) from (2.1.31) and (2.1.33) one obtains the spherically symmetric form of line element of the static matter free gravitational field, derived by Schwarzschild [1916].

2.2 Solutions in different co-ordinates

The general theory of relativity proposed by [Einstein \[1915\]](#) postulates that the solutions of the gravitational field are always valid with respect to the change of co-ordinate systems by making orthogonal transformations.

2.2.1 Gullstrand co-ordinates

[Gullstrand \[1922\]](#) considers the general line element of the Einstein theory of gravity in the case of spherical symmetry with respect to the spherical polar co-ordinates

$$x_1 = r \sin \theta \cos \phi, x_2 = r \sin \theta \sin \phi, x_3 = r \cos \theta, \text{ such that } r^2 = x_1^2 + x_2^2 + x_3^2 \quad (2.2.1)$$

as

$$ds^2 = Ldu^2 + 2Mdu dr + Ndr^2 + Or^2(d\theta^2 + \sin^2 \theta d\phi^2), \quad (2.2.2)$$

where

$$u = ct,$$

and ds is a real quantity for a time-like vector. In the static instances, L, M, N and O depend only on r .

It is clearly evident that, on setting $M = 0, L = 1 - \frac{\alpha}{r}, N = \frac{-1}{L}$ and $O = -1$ in (2.2.2) reduces to the solution found by [Schwarzschild \[1916\]](#), [Droste \[1917\]](#).

Here, one chooses $g = -1$, in accordance with Einstein's gravitational equations. Let us denote $u', u'', \dots$ as the derivatives of (u, r, θ, ϕ) with respect to s and the derivatives of L, M, N, O with respect to r are denoted by $L', L'', \dots$ such that

$$\frac{dL}{ds} = L'r'$$

etc.

Using the variational method one may obtain the determinant equations

$$O^2(LN - M^2) + 1 = 0 \quad (2.2.3)$$

and

$$O^2(LN' + NL' - 2MM') - \frac{2O'}{O} = 0. \quad (2.2.4)$$

In application of (2.2.3) and (2.2.4) it may be easy to derive the equations of geodesic worldlines.

Furthermore, for $g = -1$, the contracted Christoffel tensor $B_{\mu\nu} = R_{\mu\nu}$ is defined by

$$B_{\mu\nu} = R_{\mu\nu} = - \sum_{\sigma} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_{\sigma}} \Gamma_{\mu\nu}^{\sigma} + \sum_{\alpha\beta} \Gamma_{\mu\alpha}^{\beta} \Gamma_{\nu\beta}^{\alpha}, \quad (2.2.5)$$

where $\Gamma_{\mu\nu}^{\sigma}$ denotes the 3-index symbol. Now taking the second derivative of (2.2.1) and solving the equation (2.2.5) on calculating 3-index symbols, one may obtain all the components of $R_{\mu\nu}$. But for static case, Einstein's theory of gravity states that

$$R_{\mu\nu} = 0. \quad (2.2.6)$$

So, solving all the components of $R_{\mu\nu}$ in consideration with (2.2.6), we obtain

$$O = - \left(1 - \frac{\beta}{r^3}\right)^{2/3}, \quad L = 1 - \frac{\alpha}{r\sqrt{-O}}, \quad O^2(LN - M^2) + 1 = 0. \quad (2.2.7)$$

Equation (2.2.7) represents the general solution of the one-body problem. Here, β can be chosen arbitrarily, while α is determined by Newton's theory.

Then, considering the redshift of the spectral lines which bend the light rays in the gravitational field of the Sun (β -independent), it is possibly characterized (2.2.7) for the perihelion procession as

$$N = O = -1, \quad M = \sqrt{\frac{\alpha}{r}}. \quad (2.2.8)$$

Now, substituting (2.2.8) in (2.2.2), the line element one obtains

$$ds^2 = \left(1 - \frac{\alpha}{r}\right) du^2 + 2\sqrt{\frac{\alpha}{r}} du dr - dr^2 - r^2 (d\theta^2 + \sin^2 \theta d\phi^2). \quad (2.2.9)$$

2.2.2 Eddington co-ordinates

While making a comparison of Whitehead [1923]'s and Einstein [1915]'s theory of gravitation, Eddington [1924] observed that from the Schwarzschild [1916] metric solution for a particle at rest in the gravitational field, t corresponds to a synchronisation of time, under the condition that the outward velocity of light is equal to the inward velocity.

For a particle at rest at the origin corresponding spherically symmetric metric solution given by Schwarzschild [1916]

$$ds^2 = \left(1 - \frac{2m}{r}\right) dt^2 - \left(1 - \frac{2m}{r}\right)^{-1} dr^2 - r^2 (d\theta^2 + \sin^2 \theta d\phi^2). \quad (2.2.10)$$

Further, introducing a new co-ordinate t^* given by

$$t^* = t - 2m \log(r - m) \quad (2.2.11)$$

the expression (2.2.10) reduces to

$$ds^2 = dt^{*2} - dr^2 - \left(\frac{2m}{r}\right) (dt^* - dr)^2 - r^2 (d\theta^2 + \sin^2 \theta d\phi^2). \quad (2.2.12)$$

If we set $ds = 0$ in (2.2.12) it is found that for the co-ordinates (r, t^*) the outward velocity of light in a radial direction is unity; the inward velocity depends on R .

Furthermore, if one takes the transformation on radial co-ordinate as

$$r = \left(1 + \frac{m}{2r_*}\right)^2 r_*; \quad (2.2.13)$$

so that

$$dr = \left(1 - \frac{m^2}{4r_*^2}\right) dr_*. \quad (2.2.14)$$

Then the general static line element, one gets

$$ds^2 = \left(\frac{1 - m/2r_*}{1 + m/2r_*}\right)^2 dt^2 - \left(1 + \frac{m}{2r_*}\right)^4 \{dr_*^2 + r_*^2 (d\theta^2 + \sin^2 \theta d\phi^2)\}, \quad (2.2.15)$$

where the co-ordinates (r_*, θ, ϕ) are called isotropic polar co-ordinate. The metric solution (2.2.15) was obtained by [Eddington \[1923\]](#).

2.2.3 Lemaître co-ordinates

A transform in the spherical co-ordinate of the Schwarzschild from (t, r, θ, ϕ) to the new co-ordinates $(\tau, \xi, \theta, \phi)$ considered by [Lemaître \[1933\]](#) as

$$d\tau = dt + \sqrt{\frac{2m}{r}} \left(1 - \frac{2m}{r}\right)^{-1} dr, \quad (2.2.16)$$

$$d\xi = dt + \sqrt{\frac{r}{2m}} \left(1 - \frac{2m}{r}\right)^{-1} dr \quad (2.2.17)$$

and, on integrating, one obtains

$$\tau = t + 2\sqrt{2mr} + 2m \log \frac{\sqrt{r} - \sqrt{2m}}{\sqrt{r} + \sqrt{2m}}, \quad (2.2.18)$$

$$\xi = t - \frac{2}{3} \frac{r^{2/3}}{\sqrt{2m}}. \quad (2.2.19)$$

Then the Schwarzschild form of the field is written without singularity

$$ds^2 = d\tau^2 - \frac{2m d\xi^2}{r} - r^2 (d\theta^2 + \sin^2 \theta d\phi^2), \quad (2.2.20)$$

where

$$r = \left[\frac{3}{2} \sqrt{2m} (t - \xi)\right]^{2/3}.$$

2.2.4 Kruskal–Szekeres co-ordinates

From the well-known [Schwarzschild \[1916\]](#)'s expression for the metric around a center of mass, it can be shown that the singularities at $r = 0$ and $r = 2m$ are very different in character. This implies that $r = 2m$, in which *no real singularity* exhibits, can be demonstrated by a choice of co-ordinates seemingly simpler and more explicit. The singularity is clearly caused by the co-ordinate system rather than by any irregularities in the manifold itself.

It was [Kruskal \[1960\]](#) and [Szekeres \[1960\]](#), who made an attempt to understand the cause of singularities due to Schwarzschild co-ordinate (t, r, θ, ϕ) . They both had individually obtained the metric solutions, which is free from the *no real singularity* at $r = 2m$ and exhibits the actual singularity at $r = 0$ only.

[Kruskal \[1960\]](#) considered the co-ordinate transformation as

$$\begin{aligned} u &= \left(\frac{r}{2m} - 1\right)^{1/2} e^{r/4m} \cosh\left(\frac{t}{4m}\right), \\ v &= \left(\frac{r}{2m} - 1\right)^{1/2} e^{r/4m} \sinh\left(\frac{t}{4m}\right), \end{aligned} \quad (2.2.21)$$

where as the inverse transformation to Schwarzschild co-ordinates (t, r, θ, ϕ) is defined by

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\frac{r}{2m} - 1\right) e^{r/2m} &= u^2 - v^2, \\ \tanh\left(\frac{t}{4m}\right) &= \frac{u}{v}. \end{aligned} \quad (2.2.22)$$

Then the metric solution of the static matter free gravitational field, one may obtain

$$ds^2 = \frac{32m^3}{r} e^{-r/2m} (du^2 - dv^2) + r^2 (d\theta^2 + \sin^2 \theta d\phi^2). \quad (2.2.23)$$

As the [Schwarzschild \[1916\]](#) field consists of two disjoint regions, $0 < r < 2m$ and $r > 2m$, separated by the singular hypercylinder $r = 2m$, one may consider the [Szekeres \[1960\]](#) co-ordinate transformation by the following relation

$$\begin{aligned} u &= 2 \left(\frac{r}{2m} - 1\right)^{1/2} \exp\left(\frac{r}{4m} - \frac{1}{2}\right) \cosh\left(\frac{t}{4m}\right), \\ v &= 2 \left(\frac{r}{2m} - 1\right)^{1/2} \exp\left(\frac{r}{4m} - \frac{1}{2}\right) \sinh\left(\frac{t}{4m}\right). \end{aligned} \quad (2.2.24)$$

Then in the new [Szekeres \[1960\]](#) co-ordinate system, the line element one obtains

$$ds^2 = \frac{8m^3}{r} \exp\left(1 - \frac{r}{4m}\right) (du^2 - dv^2) + r^2 (d\theta^2 + \sin^2 \theta d\phi^2), \quad (2.2.25)$$

where

$$4 \left(1 - \frac{r}{4m}\right) \exp\left(1 - \frac{r}{4m}\right) = u^2 - v^2. \quad (2.2.26)$$

The line element defined in (2.2.25) is only valid for $u^2 > v^2$, $u > 0$, which is also regular in a whole neighbourhood of the line $u = r$, $\theta = 0$, $\phi = 0$, indeed for $u^2 - v^2 > \frac{-4}{e}$ and $\frac{-\pi}{2} < \theta < \frac{\pi}{2}$, $\pi < \phi < \pi$.

2.3 Some extensions of Symmetric Solutions

2.3.1 Metric solutions by Painlevé

Painlevé [1921] considers the line element that satisfies the static Einstein's gravitational field in spherical polar co-ordinates as

$$ds^2 = \left(1 - \frac{2\mu}{f}\right) dt^2 - f^2(d\theta^2 + \sin^2 \theta d\phi^2) - \frac{f'^2}{\left(1 - \frac{2\mu}{f}\right)} dr^2, \quad (2.3.1)$$

where μ is a constant and f is an arbitrary function of r and if r tends to ∞ , f' must be positive and tends to unity.

If one chooses f such that, it satisfies the condition of the rigorous law of gravitation studied by Einstein [1915] as

$$\frac{f^2}{1 - \frac{2\mu}{f}} = r^2,$$

then the line element (2.3.1) becomes

$$ds^2 = \left(1 - \frac{2\mu}{f}\right) \{dt^2 - r^2(d\theta^2 + \sin^2 \theta d\phi^2)\} - \frac{f'^2}{\left(1 - \frac{2\mu}{f}\right)} dr^2. \quad (2.3.2)$$

On setting $f = r$ in (2.3.2), we write

$$ds^2 = \left(1 - \frac{2\mu}{r}\right) \{dt^2 - r^2(d\theta^2 + \sin^2 \theta d\phi^2)\} - \frac{dr^2}{\left(1 - \frac{2\mu}{r}\right)}. \quad (2.3.3)$$

Again by the condition of radial differential, one can consider

$$\frac{f'^2}{1 - \frac{2\mu}{f}} = 1, \quad (2.3.4)$$

where approximates

$$f = r \left(1 - \frac{\mu}{r} \log \frac{r}{\mu}\right). \quad (2.3.5)$$

By the substitution of (2.3.5) in the line element (2.3.2), one obtains

$$ds^2 = \left(1 - \frac{2\mu}{r}\right) dt^2 - dr^2 - r^2 \left(1 - \frac{2\mu}{r} \log \frac{r}{\mu}\right) (d\theta^2 + \sin^2 \theta d\phi^2). \quad (2.3.6)$$

On setting the condition even more

$$\frac{f'^2}{\left(1 - \frac{2\mu}{f}\right)^2} = 1, \quad (2.3.7)$$

i.e, approximately, we get

$$f = r \left(1 - \frac{2\mu}{r} \log \frac{r}{\mu}\right). \quad (2.3.8)$$

This implies that the line element (2.3.2), one may get

$$ds^2 = \left(1 - \frac{2\mu}{r}\right) (dt^2 - dr^2) - r^2 \left(1 - \frac{4\mu}{r} \log \frac{r}{\mu}\right) (d\theta^2 + \sin^2 \theta d\phi^2). \quad (2.3.9)$$

2.3.2 Extensions by Birkhoff

In terms of spherical co-ordinate, the line element that satisfies the Einstein's static gravitational field, considered by [Birkhoff and Langer \[1923\]](#) is

$$ds^2 = \lambda (dt^2 - dr^2) + \gamma (d\theta^2 + \sin^2 \theta d\phi^2), \quad (2.3.10)$$

where λ and γ are functions of r and t only.

Note that for the sake of comparison the line element for isotropic space-time in terms of spherical co-ordinates is

$$ds^2 = dt^2 - dr^2 - r^2 (d\theta^2 + \sin^2 \theta d\phi^2), \quad (2.3.11)$$

indicating that in the instance of interest, λ is positive and γ is negative.

The first aspect that is discovered from the definition of metric tensor ($g_{\mu\nu}$) considering the line element (2.3.10) right away is that

$$g^{11} = -g^{22} = \frac{1}{\lambda}, \quad g^{33} = \frac{1}{\gamma}, \quad g^{44} = \frac{1}{\gamma \sin^2 \theta}, \quad g^{\mu\nu} = 0 (\mu \neq \nu). \quad (2.3.12)$$

Assume that the field is independent of the apparent time, i.e, that λ and γ are functions of r only. Consider the empty space in the gravitational field where the conditions for the contracted Riemann tensor $R_{\mu\nu} = 0$ hold.

Following such conditions for the empty space, one can immediately obtain the field equations as

$$-\frac{\lambda''}{2\lambda} + \frac{\lambda'^2}{2\lambda^2} - \frac{\lambda' \gamma'}{2\lambda\gamma} = 0, \quad (2.3.13)$$

$$\frac{\lambda''}{2\lambda} - \frac{\lambda'^2}{2\lambda^2} + \frac{\gamma''}{\gamma} - \frac{\gamma'^2}{2\gamma^2} - \frac{\lambda' \gamma'}{2\lambda\gamma} = 0, \quad (2.3.14)$$

$$-\frac{\gamma''}{2\gamma} - 1 = 0, \quad (2.3.15)$$

where the accents denoted as a means of expressing differentiation with respect to r .

Now, upon admitting $\frac{\lambda}{\lambda'}$ as an integration factor and then followed by integration in (2.3.13), one obtains

$$\lambda' \gamma = \alpha \lambda, \quad (2.3.16)$$

where α is an arbitrary constant. Adding (2.3.13) and (2.3.14) yields

$$\frac{\gamma''}{\gamma} - \frac{\gamma'^2}{2\gamma^2} - \frac{\lambda' \gamma'}{\lambda\gamma} = 0, \quad (2.3.17)$$

with an integrating factor $\frac{\gamma}{\gamma'}$; and then the integration of (2.3.17) follows

$$\gamma' = -p \lambda \sqrt{-\gamma}, \quad (2.3.18)$$

where p is an integration constant. It is easy to show from the conditions of (2.3.16) and (2.3.17) in (2.3.15) that $p \neq 0$.

The introduction of a new independent variable R such that

$$dR = \frac{p\lambda}{2} dr, \quad (2.3.19)$$

implies the line element (2.3.10) as

$$ds^2 = \lambda dt^2 - \frac{4dR^2}{p^2\lambda} + \gamma(d\theta^2 + \sin^2\theta d\phi^2). \quad (2.3.20)$$

Upon precisely calculating the integration constant in R , the outcome from (2.3.16) and (2.3.18) are

$$\gamma = -R^2, \quad \lambda = \frac{2\alpha}{pR} + b, \quad (2.3.21)$$

where b is the constant of integration. Substituting (2.3.21) in (2.3.20) one obtains the most general static solution in the empty space of the field of gravitation as

$$ds^2 = \left(b + \frac{2\alpha}{pR}\right) dt^2 - \frac{4dR^2}{(bp^2 + \frac{2\alpha p}{R})} - R^2(d\theta^2 + \sin^2\theta d\phi^2). \quad (2.3.22)$$

If one sets the unit of time t as to coincide with the second for a particle at rest at infinity, while the unit of radial length is the light-second. This condition requires $b = 1$, $p^2 = 4$ and then (2.3.22) reduces to the line element (2.1.9) obtained by Schwarzschild [1916] and Droste [1917].

2.3.3 Einstein - Rosen Bridge

If a reference system is evenly accelerated in a gravitationally free space, it can be considered to be *at rest*, so long as the space's state as understood to be that of a homogeneous gravitational field.

If one considers the metric field

$$ds^2 = \alpha^2 x_1^2 dx_4^2 - (dx_1^2 + dx_2^2 + dx_3^2), \quad (2.3.23)$$

so that $g_{\mu\nu}$ of the field satisfy in the general equations

$$R_{ij} = 0, \quad (2.3.24)$$

where $g_{\mu\nu}$ corresponding to (2.3.23) are regular for all finite points of space-time. It is evident that for $x_1 = 0$ the determinant g of the $g_{\mu\nu}$ vanishes. Hence the hyperplane $x_1 = 0$ from the standpoint of (2.3.24) represents a singularity of the field.

If one replaces (2.3.24) by

$$R_{ij}^* = g^2 R_{ij} = 0, \quad (2.3.25)$$

so that in $g^2 R_{ij}$ there is no longer any denominator and this system of equations is satisfied by (2.3.23) at all finite points.

The well-known spherically symmetric static solution of the gravitational equations obtained by Schwarzschild [1916] is

$$ds^2 = \left(1 - \frac{2m}{r}\right) dt^2 - \left(1 - \frac{2m}{r}\right)^{-1} dr^2 - r^2 (d\theta^2 + \sin^2 \theta d\phi^2), \quad (2.3.26)$$

($r > 2m$, θ from 0 to π , ϕ from 0 to 2π); and the co-ordinate (r, θ, ϕ, t) is called Schwarzschild spherical co-ordinate. For $r = 2m$ in (2.3.26) the g_{11} becomes infinite, so one has there a singularity.

Einstein and Rosen [1935] introduce a new variable u in place of r such that

$$u^2 = r - 2m \quad (2.3.27)$$

so that the expression (2.3.26) becomes

$$ds^2 = \frac{u^2}{u^2 + 2m} dt^2 - 4(u^2 + 2m) du^2 - (u^2 + 2m)^2 (d\theta^2 + \sin^2 \theta d\phi^2). \quad (2.3.28)$$

However, for all values of the variables these new $g_{\mu\nu}$ are regular functions such that for $u = 0$, g_{44} vanishes, hence also the determinant g . It is clear that the solution of the new field equations is free from singularities for all finite points.

Comparing (2.3.27) and (2.3.28), one notices that r varies from $+\infty$ to $2m$ and then again from $2m$ to ∞ as u varies from $-\infty$ to $+\infty$. If one tries to describe mathematically that a hyperplane $r = 2m$ or $u = 0$ in which g vanishes, then that joins the four dimensional space by two congruent parts or *sheets*. Those *sheets* are known as *Einstein - Rosen bridge* described by the solution (2.3.28) corresponding to (2.3.27).

2.3.4 Synge tetrad extension

Let (u, v) be two variables ranging from $-\infty$ to $+\infty$. Throughout this subsection, we suppose $u^2 - v^2 > 0$, $u > 0$ such that certain functions of $(u^2 - v^2)$ can be used to derive the line element of the static matter free gravitational field.

Synge [1950], using a series approach, defined Ψ as a function of $(u^2 - v^2)$ by

$$\Psi = f(u^2 - v^2), \quad (2.3.29)$$

for which he assumed

$$\Psi = \xi^2 \quad (\xi \geq 0) \quad \text{if} \quad \Psi \geq 0 \quad \text{and} \quad u^2 - v^2 \geq 0. \quad (2.3.30)$$

Then he formulated the following relations as

$$u^2 - v^2 = \alpha^2 (\xi + \sinh \xi \cosh \xi)^2, \quad (2.3.31)$$

from which

$$r = \alpha \cosh^2 \xi \quad (2.3.32)$$

and

$$F = \frac{1}{(u^2 - v^2)} \left(1 - \frac{4\alpha^2 \tanh^2 \xi}{u^2 - v^2} \right). \quad (2.3.33)$$

Here α is a positive constant.

It is observed from (2.3.33) with regards to (2.3.31) that, for $u^2 - v^2 > 0$, the sign of F is the same as that of

$$(\xi + \sinh \xi \cosh \xi)^2 - 4 \tanh^2 \xi,$$

which is the same as that of

$$\xi + \sinh \xi \cosh \xi - 2 \tanh \xi.$$

Since $\xi > \tanh \xi$ and $\sinh \xi \cosh \xi > \tanh \xi$, this is positive, which implies $F > 0$ if $u^2 - v^2 > 0$. Clearly, F tends to zero as $u^2 - v^2$ tends to $+\infty$.

Then the new general line element obtained by Synge [1950] in a tetrad of values (u, v, θ, ϕ) is

$$ds^2 = du^2 - dv^2 + (vdu - udv)^2 F + r^2 (d\theta^2 + \sin^2 \theta d\phi^2), \quad (2.3.34)$$

F and r being functions of $(u^2 - v^2)$ as defined in (2.3.32) and (2.3.33), respectively.

If g being the determinant of the fundamental tensor, then for (2.3.34) the substitution of (2.3.33) yields

$$g = -4\alpha^4 \cosh^4 \xi \frac{\sinh^2 2\xi}{(2\xi + \sinh 2\xi)^2} \sin^2 \theta. \quad (2.3.35)$$

Applying the Synge [1950] co-ordinate transformation

$$\begin{aligned} u &= R \cosh \left(\frac{t}{2\alpha} \right), \\ v &= R \sinh \left(\frac{t}{2\alpha} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (2.3.36)$$

such that (R being positive)

$$\begin{aligned} u^2 - v^2 &= R^2, \\ du^2 - dv^2 &= dR^2 - \frac{R^2 dt^2}{4\alpha^2}, \\ udv - vdu &= \frac{R^2}{2\alpha} dt, \end{aligned} \quad (2.3.37)$$

in the line element (2.3.34), one obtains

$$ds^2 = dR^2 - \frac{(1 - FR^2) R^2}{4\alpha^2} dt^2 + r^2 (d\theta^2 + \sin^2 \theta d\phi^2), \quad (2.3.38)$$

where r being a function of R^2 given by (2.3.32) and F being a function of R^2 given by (2.3.33) as well.

If one takes the [Synge \[1950\]](#) substitution by

$$R^2 = \alpha^2 (\xi + \sinh \xi \cosh \xi)^2 \quad (2.3.39)$$

so that by (2.3.32)

$$\begin{aligned} 1 - \frac{\alpha}{r} &= \tanh^2 \xi, \\ dR^2 &= \frac{dr^2}{1 - \frac{\alpha}{r}}, \end{aligned} \quad (2.3.40)$$

and by (2.3.33)

$$\begin{aligned} 1 - FR^2 &= \frac{4\alpha^2 \tanh^2 \xi}{R^2} \\ &= \left(1 - \frac{\alpha}{r}\right) \frac{4\alpha^2}{R^2}, \end{aligned} \quad (2.3.41)$$

to the line element (2.3.38), then it reduces to the exterior solution obtained by [Schwarzschild \[1916\]](#) for a static matter free gravitational field.

2.3.5 Isotropic extension by Nariai

The field equations in the empty homogeneous static universe given by [Einstein \[1915\]](#) are

$$R_{\mu\nu} = 0, \quad (2.3.42)$$

where $R_{\mu\nu}$ is the contracted Riemann-Christoffel tensor.

[Nariai \[1951\]](#) extended the [Schwarzschild \[1916\]](#)'s exterior solution of the of the field equation (2.3.42) through considering the static isotropic line element that exhibits spherical symmetry. The line element he considered as

$$ds^2 = e^\nu dt^2 - e^\mu \{dr^2 + r^2 (d\theta^2 + \sin^2 \theta d\phi^2)\}, \quad (2.3.43)$$

where $\mu = \mu(r)$ and $\nu = \nu(r)$.

Following system of differential equations is what results from the reduction of its field equations (2.3.42) for the empty matter distribution.

$$\mu'' + \frac{\nu''}{2} + \frac{\nu'^2}{4} - \frac{\mu' \nu'}{4} + \frac{\mu'}{r} = 0, \quad (2.3.44)$$

$$\frac{\mu''}{2} + \frac{\mu'^2}{4} + \frac{\mu' \nu'}{4} + \frac{\nu' + 3\mu'}{2r} = 0, \quad (2.3.45)$$

$$\frac{\nu''}{2} + \frac{\nu'^2}{4} + \frac{\mu' \nu'}{4} + \frac{\nu'}{r} = 0, \quad (2.3.46)$$

where primes denote differentiation with respect to r .

Taking the difference of (2.3.44) and (2.3.46), one gets

$$\mu'' - \frac{\mu' \nu'}{2} + \frac{\mu' - \nu'}{r} = 0. \quad (2.3.47)$$

The introduction of integration to (2.3.47) gives

$$\mu' = \frac{2(Ae^{\nu/2} - 1)}{r}, \quad (2.3.48)$$

where A is an integration constant. For the sake of brevity, consider $A = 1$ and then substituting (2.3.48) into (2.3.45), one can get after suitable arrangements

$$\alpha'' + \frac{\alpha'(1 - \alpha)}{r} + \frac{\alpha(1 - \alpha^2)}{r^2} = 0, \quad (2.3.49)$$

where $\alpha = e^{\nu/2}$. However, solving the differential equation (2.3.49), it can be easily shown that

$$\alpha = \frac{1 - \frac{a}{r}}{1 + \frac{a}{r}}, \quad (2.3.50)$$

where a is an integration constant. If one assumes that the total mass of the empty homogeneous static universe is constant, i.e (say) m , then substituting $a = 2m$ in (2.3.50), one may get

$$e^\nu = \left(\frac{1 - \frac{2m}{r}}{1 + \frac{2m}{r}} \right)^2, \quad (2.3.51)$$

and following from the solution of linear differential equation (2.3.48), one obtains

$$e^\mu = R^2 \left(1 + \frac{2m}{r} \right)^4. \quad (2.3.52)$$

Here R^2 is any arbitrary constant obtained from the integration.

Now, substituting (2.3.51) and (2.3.52) in the line element (2.3.42), one gets

$$ds^2 = \left(\frac{1 - \frac{2m}{r}}{1 + \frac{2m}{r}} \right)^2 dt^2 - \left(1 + \frac{2m}{r} \right)^4 R^2 \{ dr^2 + r^2 (d\theta^2 + \sin^2 \theta d\phi^2) \}. \quad (2.3.53)$$

2.3.6 Finkelstein's asymmetrical extension

Finkelstein [1958] presented an analytic extension of the Schwarzschild [1916] exterior solution in a closed form valid throughout empty space-time that possesses no irregularities except at the origin. Considering an analytic manifold and an analytic quadratic form $g_{\mu\nu}$ of correct signature, Finkelstein defined a gravitational universe for the free space equation provided by Einstein [1915].

Assume that a universe containing one point particle is associated with the manifold $\mathfrak{M}$. It is evident that Schwarzschild [1916]'s line element is analytic throughout

$\mathfrak{M}$ only for a particle of negative mass. [Finkelstein \[1958\]](#) defined the line element on the manifold $\mathfrak{M}$ as

$$ds^2 = (1 - r^{-1}) dt^2 + \frac{2}{r} dt dr - (1 + r^{-1}) dr^2 - (dx_i dx_i - dr^2). \quad (2.3.54)$$

Here the abbreviations $r = (x_i x_i)^{1/2}$, so that $dr = r^{-1} x_i dx_i$ such that $i = 1, 2, 3$ were convenient. Note that $g_{\mu\nu}$ has determinant

$$\det g \equiv 1, \quad (2.3.55)$$

such that it is analytic in $\mathfrak{M}$.

One can observe that the manifold described by the [Schwarzschild \[1916\]](#) exterior solution is a proper subset of the analytic, complete manifold $\mathfrak{M}$ with metric defined in (2.3.54). As we consider for exterior solution, so for $r > 0$, the co-ordinate transformation

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{t} &= t + \ln(r - 1), \\ \bar{x}_i &= x_i, \end{aligned} \quad (2.3.56)$$

is well defined and makes the transformation to (2.3.54) as

$$ds^2 = (1 - \bar{r}^{-1}) d\bar{t}^2 - (1 - \bar{r}^{-1})^{-1} d\bar{r}^2 - (d\bar{x}_i d\bar{x}_i - d\bar{r}^2), \quad (2.3.57)$$

where this is the [Schwarzschild \[1916\]](#) line element and thus $\bar{R}_{\mu\nu} = 0$, $\bar{r} > 1$.

Casual influences propagating into the future (increasing t) can only cross the Schwarzschild surface in an outward direction in the manifold $\mathfrak{M}$ with the line element (2.3.54). As a result, the surface $r = 1$ is a real unidirectional membrane across which casual influences may only flow in one direction. This highlights the asymmetry between the past and the future.

Chapter 3

Axially Symmetric Solutions

3.1 Weyl Metric

3.1.1 Curzon's solutions

If the matter is absent then gravitational equations introduced by [Einstein \[1915\]](#) are

$$G_{mn} = 0,$$

for which

$$G_{mn} = \sum_l \frac{\partial \Gamma_{mn}^l}{\partial x_l} + \sum_{il} \Gamma_{mi}^l \Gamma_{nl}^i = 0, \quad (3.1.1)$$

where Γ_{mn}^l denote the Christoffel's 3-index symbol which characterize the components of the gravitational field.

[Curzon \[1925\]](#) found the exact solutions analogue to [Weyl \[1917\]](#) metric (line element) for the static gravitational field equations (3.1.1) by making use of the bipolar co-ordinate method which is symmetrical about z -axis in cylindrical co-ordinates. He considered the line element in cylindrical co-ordinates symmetrical about the z -axis as

$$ds^2 = -e^\lambda(dr^2 + dz^2) - r^2 e^{-\rho} d\theta^2 + e^\rho dt^2, \quad (3.1.2)$$

where λ and ρ are functions of z and r only. One may obtain the components of Einstein tensors considering the line element (3.1.1) by using (3.1.2).

In cylindrical coordinates, symmetrical along the axis of z , the equation $G_{44} = 0$ equals $\nabla^2 \rho = 0$. Hence a solution of $G_{44} = 0$ is given by

$$\rho = \frac{-2m_1}{r_1} - \frac{2m_2}{r_2}, \quad (3.1.3)$$

where r_1, r_2 are bipolar co-ordinates of a point P referred to two origins A and B on the z -axis and m_1 & m_2 being constants of integration.

From $G_{12} = 0$, we obtain

$$\lambda_z + \rho_z = r \rho_z \rho_r = \mu_z \quad (\text{say}), \quad (3.1.4)$$

and for $G_{22} = 0$, we obtain

$$\lambda_r + \rho_r = \frac{r}{2}(\rho_r^2 - \rho_z^2) = \mu_r \quad (\text{say}), \quad (3.1.5)$$

where the subscript z and r denote for $\frac{\partial}{\partial z}$ and $\frac{\partial}{\partial r}$, respectively.

Taking the transformation $r_1^2 = (z - a)^2 + r^2$ and $r_2^2 = (z + a)^2 + r^2$ with regards to (3.1.3) followed by solving the total differential equation, we obtain

$$\mu = \frac{-r^2 m_1^2}{r_1^4} - \frac{r^2 m_2^2}{r_2^4} + \left\{ \frac{z^2 + r^2 - a^2}{r_1 r_2} - 1 \right\} \frac{m_1 m_2}{a^2}, \quad (3.1.6)$$

choosing the constant of integration so that μ vanishes at infinity.

Assuming $r_1 = \frac{r}{\sin \theta_1}$ and $r_2 = \frac{r}{\sin \theta_2}$, we get

$$\mu = \frac{-m_1^2 \sin^2 \theta_1}{r_1^2} - \frac{-m_2^2 \sin^2 \theta_2}{r_2^2} - \frac{2m_1 m_2}{a^2} \sin^2 \left\{ \frac{\theta_1 - \theta_2}{2} \right\}, \quad (3.1.7)$$

where θ_1 and θ_2 are the angles made by AP and BP with the axis of z . Considering (3.1.7) in (3.1.4) and (3.1.5) and then solving, we obtain

$$\lambda = \mu - \rho. \quad (3.1.8)$$

One may generalize this solution for two singularities on the axis of z to any number of collinear singularities. Hence, the line element (metric solution) (3.1.2) will be

$$ds^2 = e^\rho dt^2 - e^{-\rho} \{ e^\mu (dr^2 + dz^2) + r^2 d\theta^2 \}, \quad (3.1.9)$$

which is a Weyl-type metric (line element) for static gravitational equations.

3.1.2 Andress' solutions

[Andress \[1930\]](#) found the solutions of Einstein's gravitational equations $G_{mn} = 0$ which give the field due to any static distribution of the matter symmetrical about an axis. He obtained the same Weyl-type metric solutions by using a simple and elegant method instead of using Curzon's bipolar co-ordinate method.

The ground form (metric solution) in cylindrical co-ordinate system that satisfies the Einstein's gravitational equations he considered as

$$ds^2 = -e^\lambda dz^2 - e^\mu dr^2 - r^2 e^\nu d\theta^2 + e^\rho dt^2 \quad (3.1.10)$$

where λ, μ, ν, ρ are functions of z & r . The co-ordinate z is measured parallel to the axis of symmetry. After some calculation one may obtain all the components of the contracted Riemann tensor (G_{mn}) which satisfies the theory.

By making some necessary further specializations such that $\lambda = \mu$ in effect removes all the exponential factors and $\nu = -\rho$ makes G_{33} equivalent to G_{44} so that there is one less equation to be satisfied. The G_{mn} 's are now:

$$\begin{aligned} G_{11} &= \frac{1}{2}(\lambda_{zz} + \lambda_{rr} + \frac{\lambda_r}{r} + \rho_z^2) = 0 \\ G_{12} &= \frac{1}{2}(\rho_z \rho_r - \frac{\rho_z}{r} - \frac{\lambda_z}{r}) = 0 \\ G_{22} &= \frac{1}{2}(\lambda_{zz} + \lambda_{rr} - \frac{\lambda_r}{r} - \frac{2\rho_r}{r} + \rho_r^2) = 0 \\ G_{33} &= r^2 e^{-2\rho} G_{44} = \frac{-1}{2} e^{-\lambda - \rho r^2} (\rho_{zz} + \rho_{rr} + \frac{\rho_r}{r}) = 0. \end{aligned}$$

Then, when λ and ρ are discovered, the ground form (metric solution) is

$$ds^2 = -e^\lambda (dz^2 + dr^2) - r^2 e^{-\rho} d\theta^2 + e^\rho dt^2 \quad (3.1.11)$$

The equations $G_{11} - G_{22} = 0$ and $G_{12} = 0$ reduce to the results (3.1.5) and (3.1.4), respectively, discovered by Curzon [1925]. The equation $G_{33} = 0$ reduces to

$$(\rho_{zz} + \rho_{rr} + \frac{\rho_r}{r}) = 0, \quad (3.1.12)$$

which is equivalent to Laplace's equation $\nabla^2 \rho = 0$, so that ρ is the ordinary Newtonian of the distribution of material chosen.

By defining the new function $\mu = \lambda + \rho$ of z & r such that solving the total differential equation, we obtain

$$\mu = \int_z^\infty r \rho_z \rho_r dz + \frac{1}{2} \int_r^\infty r (\rho_r^2 - \rho_z^2) dr. \quad (3.1.13)$$

It is clear that

$$\lambda = \mu - \rho, \quad (3.1.14)$$

for which ρ and λ are both to be determined.

In order for

$$\frac{\partial(\mu_z)}{\partial r} - \frac{\partial(\mu_r)}{\partial z} = 0 \quad (3.1.15)$$

to result from the exactness of the total differential equation

$$d\mu = r \rho_z \rho_r dz + \frac{r}{2} (\rho_r^2 - \rho_z^2) dr, \quad (3.1.16)$$

it must be demonstrated that a function μ exists. Additionally, it is required to demonstrate the independent satisfaction of $G_{11} = 0$ and $G_{22} = 0$. Thus from (3.1.14) the ground form (metric solution) (3.1.11) reduces to same Weyl-type metric defined in (3.1.9).

3.2 Levi-Civita Metric

The Einsteinian ds^2 (known as Weyl Metric) was introduced by Weyl [1917] as

$$ds^2 = e^{2\psi} dt^2 - e^{-2\psi} \{e^{2\gamma}(dz^2 + dr^2) + r^2 d\theta^2\}. \quad (3.2.1)$$

The metric is axially symmetric static exact solution of Einstein's field equation in general relativity. Here in (3.2.1) $\psi(r, z)$ denotes a generic symmetric potential such that r is the distance from the axis of symmetry Oz .

Levi-Civita [1917] considered the metric introduced by Weyl [1917] by adding a constant with the temporal component as

$$ds^2 = V_0^2 e^{2\psi} dt^2 - e^{-2\psi} \{e^{2\gamma}(dz^2 + dr^2) + r^2 d\theta^2\}. \quad (3.2.2)$$

Here from (3.2.2), the generic symmetric potential is a particular solution of the equation

$$\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial r} \right) + \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial z^2} = 0, \quad (3.2.3)$$

and the function $\gamma(r, z)$ satisfies the following total differential equation

$$d\gamma = r(\psi_1^2 - \psi_2^2)dr + 2r\psi_1\psi_2 dz, \quad (\psi_1 = \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial r}, \psi_2 = \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial z}). \quad (3.2.4)$$

From (3.2.2), Let

$$dl^2 = e^{-2\psi} \{e^{2\gamma}(dz^2 + dr^2) + r^2 d\theta^2\}. \quad (3.2.5)$$

γ can be set to 1 for $\psi = 1$, in which case dl^2 is a part of Euclidean space, with cylindrical coordinates r, z, θ , the last of which is clearly understood to represent the azimuthal angle around axis Oz . The θ lines in this instance are parallel circles with $r = \text{constant}$ and $z = \text{constant}$.

Let us consider a generic surface $z = \text{constant}$, the (3.2.5) becomes

$$dl^2 = e^{2(\gamma-\psi)} dr^2 + e^{-2\psi} r^2 d\theta^2.$$

Since z is now constant, the coefficients of dr^2 and $d\theta^2$ rely solely on r . This is because the r lines ($\theta = \text{const.}$) are *geodesics*, and the θ lines—that is, the *isometrics*—have *constant geodesic curvature* and are thus the *geodesic circles* of the surfaces $z = \text{constant}$.

Consider the solution of (3.2.3) (generic symmetric potential) as logarithmic potential, which is a closer analogy between the isometric and the parallel circles of ordinary space, don't depend on z . By establishing an arbitrary constant h , we write

$$\psi_1 = \frac{h}{r}, \psi_2 = 0$$

such that

$$\psi = h \log \frac{r}{r_0}, \quad (3.2.6)$$

where r_0 is an integration constant such that $\frac{r}{r_0} = e^{\frac{\psi}{h}}$, which follows that r_0 has the dimensions of length. Now (3.2.4) becomes

$$\gamma = h^2 \log \frac{r}{r_0}. \quad (3.2.7)$$

Now consider the elementary theory of Newtonian attraction. When a circular cylinder is infinitely homogeneous, it behaves as though its mass were evenly distributed along its axis, with each unit length having the same density μ . Given the distance r from the axis and constant G of attraction, by specializing the inessential additive constant, one may obtain for such a potential, the expression

$$-V_0^2 \psi = 2G\mu \log \frac{r_0}{r}. \quad (3.2.8)$$

Now substituting (3.2.6) in (3.2.8), we get

$$h = \frac{2G\mu}{V_0^2}. \quad (3.2.9)$$

Without observing any errors, the limiting value c can be substituted for V_0 . Consequently, one has in C.G.S. units

$$V_0 = c = 3 \times 10^{10} \quad \& \quad G = 6.7 \times 10^{-8},$$

and this leads to

$$h = \frac{2}{9} \times 6.7 \times 10^{-28} \mu, \quad (3.2.10)$$

where the linear density μ must be expressed in grams per centimeter.

The geodesic circles must be concave towards the centre ($r = 0$) in order to match the qualitative requirement, hence $h \ll 1$. From this point on, one observes that, given such a hypothesis, one may assume $h^2 \approx 0$ for any distribution realizable with ordinary mass.

So, from (3.2.7), we get

$$\gamma = 0. \quad (3.2.11)$$

Thus, the metric (3.2.2) can be rewritten as

$$ds^2 = V_0^2 e^{2\psi} dt^2 - e^{-2\psi} \{(dz^2 + dr^2) + r^2 d\theta^2\},$$

but $2\psi = \log\left(\frac{r}{r_0}\right)^{2h}$ and setting for brevity with the context of small h from (3.2.10)

$$r_0 = 1,$$

for which

$$2\psi = \log r^{2h}.$$

Then the line element, we obtain

$$ds^2 = V_0^2 r^{2h} dt^2 - r^{-2h} \{(dz^2 + dr^2) + r^2 d\theta^2\}, \quad (3.2.12)$$

where $V_0 = 3 \times 10^{10}$ C.G.S unit and h is defined in (3.2.10).

3.3 Chazy Metric

Weyl [1917] and Levi-Civita [1917] had given some general expressions for the static exterior line element of the gravitational field in vacuum, which also admits an axis of revolution. Later, Chazy [1924] found the expression for ds^2 (line element) by a less elegant but more direct method.

He considered the line element in cylindrical co-ordinate (x, y, t, ϕ) as

$$ds^2 = a^2 dt^2 + b^2 d\phi^2 + c^2(dx^2 + dy^2), \quad (3.3.1)$$

where a, b , and c are functions of x and y . If we put $c = e^\gamma$, such that $\gamma = \gamma(x, y)$, then the following field equations from the components of Ricci tensor, we obtain

$$2\Delta\gamma + \frac{\Delta a}{a} + \frac{\Delta b}{b} = 0, \quad (3.3.2)$$

$$\frac{\partial(ab)}{\partial y} \frac{\partial\gamma}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial(ab)}{\partial x} \frac{\partial\gamma}{\partial y} - \frac{\partial^2(ab)}{\partial x \partial y} + \frac{\partial a}{\partial x} \frac{\partial b}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial b}{\partial x} \frac{\partial a}{\partial y} = 0, \quad (3.3.3)$$

$$\frac{\partial(ab)}{\partial x} \frac{\partial\gamma}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial(ab)}{\partial y} \frac{\partial\gamma}{\partial y} - \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{\partial^2(ab)}{\partial x^2} - \frac{\partial^2(ab)}{\partial y^2} \right] + \frac{\partial a}{\partial x} \frac{\partial b}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial a}{\partial y} \frac{\partial b}{\partial y} = 0, \quad (3.3.4)$$

where $\Delta = \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial y^2}$.

Let us first assume that the product $ab = \text{constant}$. Then (3.3.3) and (3.3.4) reduces to

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial a}{\partial x} \frac{\partial b}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial b}{\partial x} \frac{\partial a}{\partial y} &= 0 \\ \frac{\partial a}{\partial x} \frac{\partial b}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial a}{\partial y} \frac{\partial b}{\partial y} &= 0. \end{aligned} \quad (3.3.5)$$

Consequently, a or b are two constants and are different from zero. Then (3.3.2) reduces to

$$\Delta\gamma = 0. \quad (3.3.6)$$

On the other hand, let $x + iy$ be an analytical function for which γ would depend on x and y . Following which we consider new variables X and Y the quotient by i of the product ab and the real part of this analytical function. Assuming ab equal to iX and replacing b by $\frac{iX}{a}$, such that the factor i will disappear from the equations obtained which are homogeneous in a and b .

So, after setting $a = e^\alpha$, the linear partial differential equation, we obtain

$$\frac{\partial^2\alpha}{\partial X^2} + \frac{\partial^2\alpha}{\partial Y^2} + \frac{1}{X} \frac{\partial\alpha}{\partial X} = 0 \quad (3.3.7)$$

Substituting the likewise expression $a = e^\alpha$, $b = iXe^{-\alpha}$ in (3.3.3) and (3.3.4), we get

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial\gamma}{\partial X} &= -\frac{\partial\alpha}{\partial X} + X \left[\left(\frac{\partial\alpha}{\partial X} \right)^2 - \left(\frac{\partial\alpha}{\partial Y} \right)^2 \right] \\ \frac{\partial\gamma}{\partial Y} &= -\frac{\partial\alpha}{\partial Y} + 2X \frac{\partial\alpha}{\partial X} \frac{\partial\alpha}{\partial Y}. \end{aligned} \quad (3.3.8)$$

And it can be seen that the condition for the integrability of (3.3.8) is precisely (3.3.7).

Hence, the line element (ds^2) of a static gravitational field admitting an axis of revolution can receive the form by a suitable choice of space co-ordinates as

$$ds^2 = e^{2\alpha} dt^2 - e^{2\beta} d\phi^2 - e^{2\gamma} (dX^2 + dY^2), \quad (3.3.9)$$

where three variables α, β and γ are functions of X and Y and are determined by (3.3.7),

$$\beta = -\alpha + \log |X| + \text{constant} \quad (3.3.10)$$

and

$$\gamma = -\alpha + \int \left\{ X \left[\left(\frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial X} \right)^2 - \left(\frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial Y} \right)^2 \right] dX + 2X \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial X} \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial Y} dY \right\} + \text{constant}. \quad (3.3.11)$$

By substituting (3.3.10) and (3.3.11) in (3.3.9) the axially symmetric line element, we obtain

$$ds^2 = e^{2\alpha} dt^2 - e^{-2\alpha} \{ e^{2\mu} l_2 (dX^2 + dY^2) + X^2 l_1 d\phi^2 \}, \quad (3.3.12)$$

where l_1 and l_2 are exponential constants and

$$\mu = \int \left\{ X \left[\left(\frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial X} \right)^2 - \left(\frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial Y} \right)^2 \right] dX + 2X \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial X} \frac{\partial \alpha}{\partial Y} dY \right\}.$$

3.4 Lewis Metric

Lewis [1932] considered a field depending upon two variables x_1 & x_2 where $x_1 = 0$ being the axis of symmetry of the field, x_0 interpreting as time co-ordinate and x_3 as an angular variable varying from 0 to 2π .

The first fundamental quadratic form he considered as

$$ds^2 = f dx_0^2 - \{ e^\mu dx_1^2 + e^\nu dx_2^2 + l dx_3^2 \} - 2m dx_0 dx_3, \quad (3.4.1)$$

in which ν will be put equal to μ after the gravitational equations had been deduced. The last term in (3.4.1) mainly represents the effect of rotation. With usual notation, he found that

$$-g = r^2 e^{\mu+\nu}, \quad \text{where} \quad r^2 = fl + m^2 \quad (3.4.2)$$

and

$$g^{00} = lr^{-2}, \quad g^{11} = -e^{-\mu}, \quad g^{22} = e^{-\nu}, \quad g^{33} = -fr^{-2}, \quad g^{03} = -mr^{-2}.$$

In the same paper, Lewis considered the *action function*, which helps to the field equations, that differing from $R\sqrt{-g}$ by the divergence of a function of the gravitational potentials and their derivatives. The *action function* is defined by

$$2G = \Gamma_{ik}^r \frac{\partial}{\partial x_r} (g^{ik} \sqrt{-g}) - \Gamma_{ir}^r \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} (g^{ik} \sqrt{-g}), \quad (3.4.3)$$

where Γ_{lm}^k is Christoffel's 3-index symbol and $g^{mn} = \frac{1}{g_{mn}}$ is the inverse of metric tensor. After finding out all the components of gravitational field (3-index symbols) and inserting then in (3.4.3), we obtain

$$2G = e^{-(\mu-\nu)/2} \left(\frac{f_1 l_1 + m_1^2}{r} + 2r_1 \nu_1 \right) + e^{(\mu-\nu)/2} \left(\frac{f_2 l_2 + m_2^2}{r} + 2r_2 \mu_2 \right) \quad (3.4.4)$$

where the suffix 1 denotes $\frac{\partial}{\partial x_1}$ and 2 denotes $\frac{\partial}{\partial x_2}$.

By virtue of (3.4.2) and putting $\nu = \mu$ with carrying out the variation in action function, one may obtain

$$\nabla^2 \mu = \frac{1}{2r^2} \{[f, l] + [m, m]\}, \quad (3.4.5)$$

where

$$[\alpha, \beta] \equiv \alpha_1 \beta_1 + \alpha_2 \beta_2$$

and

$$\nabla^2 = \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x_1^2} + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x_2^2},$$

such that

$$\mu_1 = -\frac{1}{2r} \{f_1 l_1 + m_1^2 - (f_2 l_2 + m_2^2)\}, \quad (3.4.6)$$

and for the contracted Riemann tensor $R_{12} = 0$, we get

$$\mu_2 = -\frac{1}{2r} \{f_1 l_2 + f_2 l_1 + 2m_1 m_2\}, \quad (3.4.7)$$

where m can be determined from (3.4.2) followed by the extracting of f and l which will satisfy

$$m_{11} + m_{22} - \frac{m_1}{r} = -\frac{m}{r^2} \{[f, l] + [m, m]\} \quad (3.4.8)$$

identically. Consequently, from (3.4.6) and (3.4.7), we can therefore obtain

$$\mu = -\int \frac{1}{2r} \{f_1 l_1 + m_1^2 - (f_2 l_2 + m_2^2)\} dr + \frac{1}{2r} \{f_1 l_2 + f_2 l_1 + 2m_1 m_2\} dz. \quad (3.4.9)$$

The condition for the existence for such function μ exists is that the total differential equation containing μ is exact for which one easily verifies that $\mu_{12} - \mu_{21} = 0$.

Lewis, then considered the linear transformation of the differentials of the coordinates which is purely local, i.e, non-integrable. The transformations are

$$dx_0 = dt = dt' \cosh u - d\theta' \sinh u, \quad dx_3 = d\theta = d\theta' \cosh u - dt' \sinh u \quad (3.4.10)$$

and taking

$$\begin{aligned} f &= F \cosh^2 u - L \sinh^2 u, \\ l &= L \cosh^2 u - F \sinh^2 u, \\ m &= \frac{1}{2}(L - F) \sinh 2u, \end{aligned} \quad (3.4.11)$$

it can be easily shown that

$$fl + m^2 = FL = r^2. \quad (3.4.12)$$

Now, substituting (3.4.10) and (3.4.11) by virtue of (3.4.12) in (3.4.1), we get

$$ds^2 = Fdt'^2 - \{e^\mu(dr^2 + dz^2) + Ld\theta^2\}. \quad (3.4.13)$$

The relation (3.4.12) suggests that

$$F = re^{-\lambda}, \quad L = re^\lambda. \quad (3.4.14)$$

Following the metric (3.4.13) the action function (3.4.4), we obtain

$$2G = \frac{1}{r} - r[\lambda, \lambda] + 4r \sinh^2 \lambda [u, u] + 2[r, \mu], \quad (3.4.15)$$

where λ and μ satisfies the following equations obtained from variation of action function as

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r \frac{\partial \lambda}{\partial r} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left(r \frac{\partial \lambda}{\partial z} \right) + 2r \sinh 2\lambda [u, u] = 0, \quad (3.4.16)$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r \sinh^2 \lambda \frac{\partial u}{\partial r} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left(r \sinh^2 \lambda \frac{\partial u}{\partial z} \right) = 0, \quad (3.4.17)$$

such that the special set of solutions one may obtain as

$$u = \text{constant}, \quad \lambda = \log r - 2\psi. \quad (3.4.18)$$

Here F and L are identical with f and l found by Weyl [1917] in the static case. From (3.4.18) and (3.4.14), we obtain

$$F = e^{2\psi}, \quad L = e^{-2\psi}, \quad (3.4.19)$$

from which the metric (3.4.13) becomes

$$ds^2 = e^{-2\psi} dt'^2 - \{e^\mu(dr^2 + dz^2)\} + e^{-2\psi} r^2 d\theta^2, \quad (3.4.20)$$

where ψ is the Newtonian potential of an arbitrary axially symmetric distribution of the matter in the canonical space.

3.5 Papapetrou Metric

Papapetrou [1953] considered the general line element for the static distribution in the gravitational field that was initially studied by Lewis [1932]. The line element is

$$ds^2 = f dt^2 - e^\mu(dr^2 + dz^2) - ld\phi^2 - 2md\phi dt, \quad (3.5.1)$$

where r, ϕ, z are cylindrical coordinates. The quantities μ, f, l , and m depend only on r and z .

These quantities, including (3.5.1), satisfy the following field equations:

$$\mu_r = \frac{-1}{2r}(f_r l_r - f_z l_z + m_r^2 - m_z^2) \quad (3.5.2)$$

$$l \nabla^2 f - f \nabla^2 l = \frac{1}{r}(l f_r - f l_r) \quad (3.5.3)$$

$$m \nabla^2 l - l \nabla^2 m = \frac{1}{r}(m l_r - l m_r) \quad (3.5.4)$$

$$m \nabla^2 f - f \nabla^2 m = \frac{1}{r}(m f_r - f m_r) \quad (3.5.5)$$

therefore,

$$(l + m) \left\{ \nabla^2 f - \frac{f_r}{r} \right\} - (f - m) \left\{ \nabla^2 l - \frac{l_r}{r} \right\} - (f + l) \left\{ \nabla^2 m - \frac{m_r}{r} \right\} = 0, \quad (3.5.6)$$

where $\nabla^2 = \frac{\partial^2}{\partial r^2} + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial z^2}$. Since the system is in canonical coordinate frame, so only two of the three grounds f, l, m are independent of each other. It is evident that these three quantities are connected by the following relationship:

$$fl + m^2 = r^2. \quad (3.5.7)$$

The equation (3.5.2) will be used to determine μ . It can be found that

$$\mu_z = \frac{-1}{2r}(f_r l_z + f_z l_r + 2m_r m_z). \quad (3.5.8)$$

It is simple to demonstrate that (3.5.3), (3.5.4) and (3.5.5) already ensures the compatibility of (3.5.2) and (3.5.8).

He considered the quantities f, l, m by two new ones, v, w , and expressed as:

$$f = \frac{1}{v}, \quad l = r^2 v - \frac{w^2}{v}, \quad m = \frac{w}{v}, \quad (3.5.9)$$

where (3.5.9) satisfies the equation (3.5.8). Then the field equations are reduced to the following two independent equations:

$$v(\nabla^2 v + \frac{1}{r}v_r) - (v_r^2 + v_z^2) - \frac{1}{r^2}(w_r^2 + w_z^2) = 0 \quad (3.5.10)$$

$$v(\nabla^2 w - \frac{1}{r}w_r) - 2(v_r w_r + v_z w_z) = 0. \quad (3.5.11)$$

The new solution arises by adding additional condition

$$(v_r w_r + v_z w_z) = 0 \quad (3.5.12)$$

to (3.5.11), we obtain

$$\nabla^2 w - \frac{1}{r}w_r = 0. \quad (3.5.13)$$

Taking the condition (3.5.12) and (3.5.13) in (3.5.10) and solving in detail, we obtain

$$\nabla^2 v + \frac{v_r}{r} = \frac{\alpha^2 v}{\alpha^2 v^2 - 1} (v_r^2 + v_z^2), \quad (3.5.14)$$

where α is an integration constant.

By considering a new harmonic function ψ , which satisfies the following Laplace equation

$$\nabla^2 \psi + \frac{\psi_r}{r} = 0, \quad (3.5.15)$$

one can solve and find v and w as

$$v = \alpha \cosh \psi_z + \beta \sinh \psi_z \quad (3.5.16)$$

and

$$w = \sqrt{\alpha^2 - \beta^2} r \psi_r. \quad (3.5.17)$$

Considering (3.5.9) in (3.5.2) & (3.5.8) and then following (3.5.16) and (3.5.17), one can find

$$\begin{aligned} (\mu - \log v)_r &= \frac{r}{2} (\psi_{zr}^2 - \psi_{zz}^2), \\ (\mu - \log v)_z &= r \psi_{zr} \psi_{zz}, \end{aligned} \quad (3.5.18)$$

from which the quantity $(\mu - \log v)$ will be obtained directly through integration.

Now substituting (3.5.9) in (3.5.1) by considering (3.5.7) the line element, we obtain

$$ds^2 = v^{-1} (dt - wd\phi)^2 - v r^2 d\phi^2 - e^\mu (dr^2 + dz^2). \quad (3.5.19)$$

3.6 Tiwari & Mishra Metric

In the paper published by [Tiwari and Misra \[1962\]](#), the metric solution they considered that describes the field due to bodies in stationary rotation about their axes as

$$ds^2 = A dt^2 - B d\phi^2 + 2C d\phi dt - e^{2\lambda} (dr^2 + dz^2), \quad (3.6.1)$$

where λ, A, B and C are functions of r and z only and (r, z, ϕ, t) are canonical co-ordinates.

In canonical co-ordinates followed by [Lewis \[1932\]](#), we have

$$AB + C^2 = r^2. \quad (3.6.2)$$

By taking into consideration (3.6.1) and (3.6.2), one may extract all of the components of the Einstein tensor and the Ricci tensor. The field equations to be derived for empty space-time corresponding to the Ricci tensor's components are

$$\lambda_{rr} + \lambda_{zz} = \frac{A_r B_r + A_z B_z + C_r^2 + C_z^2}{4r^2} \quad (3.6.3)$$

$$\lambda_r = \frac{A_z B_z + C_z^2 - A_r B_r - C_r^2}{4r} \quad (3.6.4)$$

$$\lambda_z = \frac{-1}{4r} (A_r B_z + A_z B_r + 2C_r C_z) \quad (3.6.5)$$

$$A_{rr} + A_{zz} - \frac{A_r}{r} + \frac{A}{r^2} (A_r B_r + A_z B_z + C_r^2 + C_z^2) \quad (3.6.6)$$

$$B_{rr} + B_{zz} - \frac{B_r}{r} + \frac{B}{r^2} (A_r B_r + A_z B_z + C_r^2 + C_z^2) \quad (3.6.7)$$

$$C_{rr} + C_{zz} - \frac{C_r}{r} + \frac{C}{r^2} (A_r B_r + A_z B_z + C_r^2 + C_z^2), \quad (3.6.8)$$

where the subscript r and z are denoted by $\frac{\partial}{\partial r}$ and $\frac{\partial}{\partial z}$, respectively. The integrability requirement of (3.6.4) and (3.6.5), that is,

$$\lambda_{rz} = \lambda_{zr},$$

may be easily proven because of (3.6.2). Also (3.6.3) is consistent with (3.6.4) and (3.6.5) in light of (3.6.2). The problem is of determining A, B and C from (3.6.2), (3.6.6), (3.6.7) and (3.6.8). λ will then be given by (3.6.4) and (3.6.5) subject to an additive constant.

Let us assume that (3.6.3), (3.6.6), (3.6.7) and (3.6.8) are consistent, so that these are solvable. For convenience, put

$$A = r e^\mu \cos \theta, \quad B = r e^{-\mu} \cos \theta, \quad C = r \cos \theta, \quad (3.6.9)$$

where μ and θ are new functions of r and z . The metric (3.6.1) must reduce to the static axially symmetric metric given by Weyl [1917] in the absence of rotation, which is the point at which C disappears, suggesting the substitution (3.6.9).

Considering (3.6.9) the reduced field equations, we obtain

$$\theta_{rr} + \theta_{zz} + \frac{\theta_r}{r} - \sin \theta \cos \theta (\mu_r^2 + \mu_z^2) = 0 \quad (3.6.10)$$

$$\mu_{rr} + \mu_{zz} + \frac{\mu_r}{r} - 2 \tan \theta (\mu_r \theta_r + \mu_z \theta_z) = 0 \quad (3.6.11)$$

$$\lambda_r = \frac{-1}{4r} - \frac{r}{4} \{ \theta_r^2 - \theta_z^2 - \cos^2 \theta (\mu_r \theta_r - \mu_z \theta_z) \} \quad (3.6.12)$$

$$\lambda_z = \frac{r}{2} (\cos^2 \theta \mu_r \mu_z - \theta_r \theta_z), \quad (3.6.13)$$

from which λ can be determined. Thus, from (3.6.9) and (3.6.1) the metric, we get

$$ds^2 = r e^\mu \cos \theta (dt^2 - e^{-2\mu} d\phi^2) + 2r \sin \theta d\phi dt - e^{2\lambda} (dr^2 + dz^2). \quad (3.6.14)$$

If we put $\theta = 0$ in (3.6.14), it reduces to the static axially symmetric metric of Weyl [1917] in canonical co-ordinates. However, by putting

$$\mu = 0 \quad (3.6.15)$$

the metric (3.6.14) reduces to

$$ds^2 = r \cos \theta (dt^2 - d\phi^2) + 2r \sin \theta d\phi dt - e^{2\lambda} (dr^2 + dz^2) \quad (3.6.16)$$

with the corresponding empty space-time field equations:

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda_r &= \frac{-1}{4r} - \frac{r}{4} (\theta_r^2 - \theta_z^2) \\ \lambda_z &= \frac{-r}{2} \theta_r \theta_z \end{aligned} \quad (3.6.17)$$

$$\theta_{rr} + \theta_{zz} + \frac{\theta_r}{r} = 0. \quad (3.6.18)$$

Equation (3.6.18) is the Laplace equation in cylindrical polar co-ordinates whose solutions are well known. Thus for every value of θ satisfying (3.6.18) we shall have a value of λ given by (3.6.17).

3.7 Kerr Type Metric Solutions

It was [Kerr \[1963\]](#), who established the metric solution for a static gravitational field in the course of a spinning mass through introducing the algebraic method for a complex null tetrad.

The stationary and axially symmetric solution that contains [Schwarzschild \[1916\]](#) metric having the mass as a constant m , obtained by [Kerr \[1963\]](#)

$$\begin{aligned} ds^2 &= (r^2 + a^2 \cos^2 \theta) (d\theta^2 + \sin^2 \theta d\phi^2) \\ &\quad + 2(du + a \sin^2 \theta d\phi) \times (dr + a \sin^2 \theta d\phi) \\ &\quad - \left(1 - \frac{2mr}{r^2 + a^2 \cos^2 \theta}\right) \times (du + a \sin^2 \theta d\phi)^2, \end{aligned} \quad (3.7.1)$$

where a is a real constant. The metric solution defined in (3.7.1) is known as *Kerr Metric*, which yields the solution for a rotating black hole, referring as *Kerr rotating black hole*.

To observe whether the Kerr metric (3.7.1) is rotating, one may find co-ordinates where this will be manifestly Minkowskian. The substitutions are

$$(r + ia)e^{i\phi} \sin \theta = x + iy, \quad r \cos \theta = z, \quad r + u = -t, \quad (3.7.2)$$

for which the rotating form of the metric,

$$ds^2 = dx^2 + dy^2 + dz^2 - dt^2 + \frac{2mr^3}{r^4 + a^2 z^2} \Theta^2, \quad (3.7.3)$$

where

$$\Theta = dt + \frac{z}{r} dz + \frac{r}{r^2 + a^2} (x dx + y dy) - \frac{a}{r^2 + a^2} (x dy - y dx)$$

and the surfaces of constant r are confocal ellipsoids of revolution about the z -axis,

$$\frac{x^2 + y^2}{r^2 + a^2} + \frac{z^2}{r^2} = 1. \quad (3.7.4)$$

Clearly, the metric is asymptotically flat, and asymptotically, r is merely the distance from the origin in the Minkowskian co-ordinates.

Chapter 4

Some Common Type Metric Solutions

In this chapter, we systematically reviewed and studied the method on obtaining the exact static field solutions of the matter free gravitational equations from symmetric about cylindrical to spherical and vice versa.

4.1 Rosen's method for a particle at rest

By using the method of [Weyl \[1917\]](#) and [Levi-Civita \[1917\]](#), one can obtain the solutions of the Einstein gravitational field equations for the case of static, axially symmetric field.

The line element in cylindrical polar co-ordinates ρ, z, ϕ and time t takes the form

$$ds^2 = e^{2\psi} dt^2 - e^{-2\psi} \{e^{2\gamma} (d\rho^2 + dz^2) + \rho^2 d\phi^2\}, \quad (4.1.1)$$

where ψ and γ are functions of ρ and z . Here ψ represents the generic Newtonian potential that satisfies the equations

$$\Delta\psi = 0, \quad (4.1.2)$$

while γ satisfies the relation

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial\gamma}{\partial\rho} &= \rho \left[\left(\frac{\partial\psi}{\partial\rho} \right)^2 - \left(\frac{\partial\psi}{\partial z} \right)^2 \right] \\ \frac{\partial\gamma}{\partial z} &= 2\rho \frac{\partial\psi}{\partial\rho} \frac{\partial\psi}{\partial z}. \end{aligned} \quad (4.1.3)$$

[Rosen \[1949\]](#) takes ψ in the form of the Newtonian potential of a rod lying on the z -axis (considered by [Bach and Wevl \[1922\]](#)) to get the Schwarzschild solution for the field of a single particle of mass m as

$$\psi_0 = \frac{1}{2} \ln \frac{r_1 + r_1 - 2m}{r_1 + r_2 + 2m}, \quad (4.1.4)$$

where $2m$ is the length of the rod and r_1 and r_2 are the distances from the ends of the rod to the point in the field. On the integration of (4.1.3) corresponding to (4.1.4), one gets

$$\gamma_0 = \frac{1}{2} \ln \frac{(r_1 + r_2)^2 - 4m^2}{4r_1 r_2}. \quad (4.1.5)$$

The meridian plane must be transformed, mean while, in order to obtain the Schwarzschild solution in its standard, spherically symmetric form.

Considering Rosen [1949]'s transformation of ρ and z to variables r and θ such that the relations

$$r = m + \frac{1}{2}(r_1 + r_2), \quad \cos \theta = \frac{(r_1 - r_2)}{2m}, \quad (4.1.6)$$

corresponding from (4.1.4) and (4.1.5), the solution (4.1.1) reduces immediately to the Schwarzschild [1916] solution with spherical polar co-ordinates (r, θ, ϕ) defined by (2.3.26).

4.2 Boyer-Lindquist maximal extension

“Pseudosingularities” that reflect merely a poor choice of co-ordinates in the metric solution of the static vacuum gravitational field equations, has been referred by *Penrose-Hawking theorem*, which Penrose [1965] and Hawking [1965] obtained individually. This sort of singularity is known to exist at $r = 2m$ in the usual form of the Schwarzschild [1916] metric; various authors (Eddington [1924], Lemaître [1933], Synge [1950], Finkelstein [1958], Kruskal [1960], Szekeres [1960]) have provided transformations to coordinate frames that eliminate this apparent singularity.

Through analyzing in some detail the empty space metric of Kerr [1963] for a stationary axially symmetric models of rotating bodies, Boyer and Lindquist [1967] established the common co-ordinate transformation method that yields the solution in the form of metric for the static vacuum gravitational field, which indeed is free from such apparent singularities.

The location of horizons, which to be defined as stationary null hypersurfaces, can be determined by such pseudosingularities like $r = 2m$ in the Schwarzschild metric. Then one notices that the event horizon contained in Kerr's solution, which in an appropriate co-ordinate system is located at

$$\begin{aligned} r^2 - 2mr + a^2 &= 0 \\ \text{i.e., } r &= m + (m^2 - a^2)^{\frac{1}{2}}, \end{aligned} \quad (4.2.1)$$

plus a true singularity again formally defined by $r = 0$.

It is evident that the metric form (3.7.3) is inconvenient for many applications, as from (3.7.4) one may notice about the complicity of r , a function of x, y, z .

To avoid such complicity, [Boyer and Lindquist \[1967\]](#) considered the suitable co-ordinate transformation

$$\begin{aligned}x &= \sqrt{(r^2 + a^2)} \sin \theta \cos [\phi - \tan^{-1}(a/r)], \\y &= \sqrt{(r^2 + a^2)} \sin \theta \sin [\phi - \tan^{-1}(a/r)], \\z &= r \cos \theta,\end{aligned}\tag{4.2.2}$$

for which the metric form (3.7.3) reduces to

$$\begin{aligned}ds^2 &= dr^2 + 2a \sin^2 \theta dr d\phi + (r^2 + a^2) \sin^2 \theta d\phi^2 \\&\quad + \rho^2 d\theta^2 - dt^2 + \frac{2mr}{\rho^2} (dr + a \sin^2 \theta d\phi + dt)^2,\end{aligned}\tag{4.2.3}$$

where

$$\rho(r, \theta) \equiv (r^2 + a^2 \cos^2 \theta)^{1/2}.\tag{4.2.4}$$

This is the generalization of the [Eddington \[1924\]](#) form (2.2.12) of the [Schwarzschild \[1916\]](#) metric (2.2.10).

The equation (3.7.4) makes it evident that the surfaces $r = \text{const}$ are confocal ellipsoids, and $\theta = \text{const}$ surfaces are hyperboloids of one sheet that are confocal to the ellipsoids based on

$$\frac{x^2 + y^2}{a^2 \sin^2 \theta} - \frac{z^2}{a^2 \cos^2 \theta} = 1.\tag{4.2.5}$$

To obtain the ‘‘Schwarzschild type’’ metric in the new form of co-ordinate system, (in the same paper) [Boyer and Lindquist \[1967\]](#) considered the transformation

$$\begin{aligned}d\bar{\phi} &= d\phi + a \frac{dr}{\beta(r)}, \\d\bar{t} &= dt - 2mr \frac{dr}{\beta(r)},\end{aligned}\tag{4.2.6}$$

so that the metric form (4.2.3) becomes

$$\begin{aligned}ds^2 &= \rho^2 \left(\frac{dr^2}{\beta} + d\theta^2 \right) + (r^2 + a^2) \sin^2 \theta d\bar{\phi}^2 \\&\quad - d\bar{t}^2 + \frac{2mr}{\rho^2} (a \sin^2 \theta d\bar{\phi} + d\bar{t})^2,\end{aligned}\tag{4.2.7}$$

where ρ^2 is defined in (4.2.4) and

$$\beta(r) \equiv r^2 - 2mr + a^2.\tag{4.2.8}$$

The metric form (4.2.7) is invariant under the transformation $\bar{\phi} \rightarrow -\bar{\phi}$, $\bar{t} \rightarrow -\bar{t}$ and reduces to the standard [Schwarzschild \[1916\]](#) metric when $a = 0$. The metric (4.2.7) features two pseudosingularities at the real zeros of $\beta(r)$, in addition to the actual singularity at $\rho^2 = 0$, which can be located later at

$$r_{\pm} = m \pm (m^2 - a^2)^{\frac{1}{2}},\tag{4.2.9}$$

and thus exist only when $a^2 \leq m^2$.

By applying the transformation

$$\begin{aligned} u + v &= \exp\left(\frac{(r+t)}{2r_+}\right), \\ \omega &= \phi + \left(\frac{a}{2mr_+}\right)t - \frac{a}{r_+} \ln\left(\frac{r-r_-}{2m}\right) \end{aligned} \quad (4.2.10)$$

corresponding to the new form of co-ordinates from the co-ordinates used in the metric form (4.2.3), Boyer and Lindquist [1967] obtained the Kruskal [1960] form of the Schwarzschild [1916] metric (in dropping all terms of order a^2) as

$$\begin{aligned} ds^2 &\simeq r^2 (d\theta^2 + \sin^2 \theta d\omega^2) + \left(\frac{32m^3}{r}\right) e^{-r/2m} (du^2 - dv^2) \\ &+ \left(\frac{4a}{r}\right) \sin^2 \theta e^{-r/2m} (r^2 + 2mr + 4m^2) d\phi (v du - u dv). \end{aligned} \quad (4.2.11)$$

The immediate application of the metric form (4.2.7) had been studied by Levy [1968] in the following year of Boyer and Lindquist [1967]'s transformation to Kerr [1963] metric. Identifying the $\bar{\phi}$ and $\bar{t}$ co-ordinates of the metric (4.2.7) and taking the Levy transformation defined by

$$\begin{aligned} e^{2u} &= 1 - \frac{2mr}{\rho^2}, \\ e^{-2k} &= 1 + \frac{m^2 \sin^2 \theta}{r^2 - 2mr + a^2 \cos^2 \theta}, \\ w &= \frac{-2mr a \sin^2 \theta}{r^2 - 2mr + a^2 \cos^2 \theta}, \\ R &= \sqrt{\beta} \sin \theta, \\ z &= (r - m) \cos \theta, \quad \bar{t} = t, \quad \bar{\phi} = \phi, \end{aligned} \quad (4.2.12)$$

where ρ and β are defined in (4.2.4) and (4.2.8), respectively, the metric form, one obtains

$$ds^2 = e^{2u} (dt + wd\phi)^2 - e^{-2u} \{e^{2k} (dR^2 + dz^2) + R^2 d\phi^2\}. \quad (4.2.13)$$

The metric form (4.2.13) is the Lewis-Papapetrou type canonical stationary axisymmetric metric.

4.3 Ernst formulation

Ernst [1968] addressed the problem of finding the uniform gravitational field for a rotating body in a possible exterior field, which is defined in the form of metric solution and obtained by Kerr [1963].

For a static matter free gravitational field, the metric form in canonical coordinate system defined by [Papapetrou \[1953\]](#) is

$$ds^2 = f^{-1} \{e^{2\gamma} (dr^2 + dz^2) + r^2 d\phi^2\} - f (dt - \omega d\phi)^2, \quad (4.3.1)$$

where f, ω and γ are functions of r and z only. Using the methods of exterior calculus that contains the Lagrangian density, governing f and ω only from (4.3.1), [Ernst \[1968\]](#) derived the homogeneous quadratic field equation containing a complex function Ψ (independent of azimuth)

$$(\Re \Psi) \nabla^2 \Psi = \nabla \Psi \cdot \nabla \Psi. \quad (4.3.2)$$

If one assumes that φ be a new potential such that

$$\Psi = f + i\varphi, \quad (4.3.3)$$

can be defined, then it must satisfy the homogeneous quadratic differential equation (4.3.2).

Among a number of simple modifications of the field equation (4.3.2), [Ernst \[1968\]](#) considered the following general substitution

$$\Psi = \frac{\xi - 1}{\xi + 1}, \quad (4.3.4)$$

so that

$$(\xi \xi^* - 1) \nabla^2 \xi = 2\xi^* \nabla \xi \cdot \nabla \xi \quad (4.3.5)$$

is well defined and derivable. It is clear that for α be any real constant, $e^{i\alpha} \xi$ is one the solution of (4.3.5) as obvious like ξ .

By introducing a new potential real function ψ that satisfies the Laplace equation

$$\nabla^2 \psi = 0, \quad (4.3.6)$$

one may consider

$$\xi = -e^{i\alpha} \coth \psi. \quad (4.3.7)$$

Naturally, the solutions discovered in this manner correspond to the well-known fields that [Weyl \[1917\]](#) ($\alpha = 0$) and [Papapetrou \[1953\]](#) ($\alpha = \frac{\pi}{2}$) investigated, respectively.

Emphasizing through [Zipoy \[1966\]](#)'s spheroidal co-ordinates rather than cylindrical co-ordinates, if one sets

$$\begin{aligned} r &= (x^2 - 1)^{1/2} (1 - y^2)^{1/2} \\ z &= xy, \end{aligned} \quad (4.3.8)$$

then the Laplacian operators assumed to be in the form

$$\nabla^2 = \frac{1}{(x^2 - y^2)} \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial x}(x^2 - 1) \frac{\partial}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial}{\partial y}(1 - y^2) \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \right]. \quad (4.3.9)$$

The form of equation (4.3.9) makes it evident that

$$\psi = \frac{1}{2} \ln \left(\frac{x - 1}{x + 1} \right) \quad \text{or} \quad \xi = x \quad (4.3.10)$$

is the solution ψ of (4.3.6). It is possible to confirm that (4.3.10) corresponds to the [Schwarzschild \[1916\]](#) field by using m as the unit of length, determining the Schwarzschild radial co-ordinate $r = x + 1$, and the angular co-ordinate $\cos \theta = y$.

When

$$\xi = x \cos \lambda + iy \sin \lambda \quad (4.3.11)$$

is found to be the solution to the differential equation (4.3.5) for any real value λ , one can then obtain the Kerr type entire metric in the form

$$ds^2 = \left[\rho^2 \left(d\theta^2 + \frac{dr^2}{\beta} \right) \right] + \left[(r^2 + a^2) \sin^2 \theta d\phi^2 - dt^2 + \frac{2mr}{\rho^2} (dt + a \sin^2 \theta d\phi)^2 \right], \quad (4.3.12)$$

where the co-ordinates are defined by

$$r = x(m^2 - a^2)^{1/2} + m, \quad \cos \theta = y \quad (4.3.13)$$

by introducing $a = \tan \lambda$ and $m = \sec \lambda$ so that the distances are measured in units of $(m^2 - a^2)^{1/2}$. Here in the metric form (4.3.12), the ρ and β are defined in the equations (4.2.4) and (4.2.8), respectively. The transformation

$$r = \sqrt{\beta} \sin \theta, \quad z = (r - m) \cos \theta \quad (4.3.14)$$

may be used to obtain the result into [Papapetrou \[1953\]](#)'s canonical form given in (4.3.1).

4.4 Tomimatsu-Sato metric

In previous section 4.3, Ernst's formulation states that one may derive stationary axisymmetric solutions in empty space from a complex function ξ , which is provided in (4.3.5).

Following [Voorhees \[1970\]](#), after four years of [Ernst \[1968\]](#)'s formulation, [Tomimatsu and Sato \[1972\]](#) established the relation between the cylindrical co-ordinates (ϱ, z) , Schwarzschild co-ordinates (r, θ) and prolate spheroidal co-ordinates (μ, ν) as

$$\begin{aligned} \varrho &= \left(\frac{mp}{\delta} \right) (\mu^2 - 1)^{1/2} (1 - \nu^2)^{1/2} = (r^2 + m^2 q^2 - 2mr)^{1/2} \sin \theta \\ z &= \left(\frac{mp}{\delta} \right) \mu \nu = (r - m) \cos \theta, \end{aligned} \quad (4.4.1)$$

where δ is a dimensionless parameter, commonly known as a deformation parameter. From (4.4.1) if J be the angular momentum and m be the gravitational mass, then

$$q = \frac{J}{m^2}, \quad p^2 + q^2 = 1. \quad (4.4.2)$$

By anticipating

$$\xi = \frac{(x+1)^\delta + (x-1)^\delta}{(x+1)^\delta - (x-1)^\delta}, \quad (4.4.3)$$

if one writes the another solution ξ of the equation (4.3.5) as a quotient of polynomials;

$$\xi = \frac{\zeta}{\vartheta}, \quad (4.4.4)$$

where ζ and ϑ are complex polynomials of μ and ν then the Ernst [1968] field equation takes the form obtained by Tomimatsu and Sato [1973] as

$$\begin{aligned} & (\mu^2 - 1)(\zeta\zeta^* - \vartheta\vartheta^*) \left(\frac{\partial^2 \zeta}{\partial \mu^2} \vartheta - \zeta \frac{\partial^2 \vartheta}{\partial \mu^2} \right) + \left(\frac{\partial \zeta}{\partial \mu} \zeta - \zeta \frac{\partial \vartheta}{\partial \mu} \right) \\ & \quad \times \left\{ 2\mu(\zeta\zeta^* - \vartheta\vartheta^*) - 2(\mu^2 - 1) \left(\zeta^* \frac{\partial \zeta}{\partial \mu} - \vartheta^* \frac{\partial \vartheta}{\partial \mu} \right) \right\} \\ & - (\nu^2 - 1)(\zeta\zeta^* - \vartheta\vartheta^*) \left(\frac{\partial^2 \zeta}{\partial \nu^2} \vartheta - \zeta \frac{\partial^2 \vartheta}{\partial \nu^2} \right) - \left(\frac{\partial \zeta}{\partial \nu} \vartheta - \zeta \frac{\partial \vartheta}{\partial \nu} \right) \\ & \quad \times \left\{ 2\nu(\zeta\zeta^* - \vartheta\vartheta^*) - 2(\nu^2 - 1) \left(\zeta^* \frac{\partial \zeta}{\partial \nu} - \vartheta^* \frac{\partial \vartheta}{\partial \nu} \right) \right\} = 0. \end{aligned} \quad (4.4.5)$$

It is evident that for $\delta = 1$ such that

$$\zeta = p\mu - iq\nu \quad \text{and} \quad \vartheta = 1, \quad (4.4.6)$$

the solution reduces to Ernst's from which in the sense of co-ordinates (r, θ) corresponding to (4.4.1), Kerr [1963] metric can be derived.

However, corresponding to (4.4.4), Tomimatsu and Sato [1972] found a new solution that satisfies the Ernst [1968] field equation (4.3.5) as

$$\xi = \frac{\zeta}{\vartheta} = \frac{p^2 \mu^4 + q^2 \nu^4 - 1 - 2ipq\mu\nu(\mu^2 - \nu^2)}{2p\mu(\mu^2 - 1) - 2iq\nu(1 - \nu^2)}, \quad (4.4.7)$$

where the deformation parameter is 2, i.e., $\delta = 2$. This solution is known as *T-S solution*.

If one writes the Lewis [1932]-Papapetrou [1953] metric

$$ds^2 = f(dt - \omega d\phi)^2 - f^{-1} \{ e^{2\gamma}(d\varrho^2 + dz^2) + \varrho^2 d\phi^2 \}, \quad (4.4.8)$$

then for the *T-S solution* and corresponding to the co-ordinates defined in (4.4.1) so that

$$f = \frac{A}{B}, \quad \omega = \frac{2mq}{A}(1 - \nu^2)C, \quad e^{2\gamma} = \frac{A}{p^4(\mu^2 - \nu^2)^4}, \quad (4.4.9)$$

it reduces to the metric obtained by [Tomimatsu and Sato \[1972\]](#) as (see [Batic \[2023\]](#))

$$ds^2 = \frac{A}{B} dt^2 - \frac{4mq(1-\nu^2)C}{B} dt d\phi - \frac{m^2 B}{4p^2(\mu^2 - \nu^2)^3} \left(\frac{d\mu^2}{\mu^2 - 1} + \frac{d\nu^2}{1 - \nu^2} \right) - \frac{m^2(1-\nu^2)}{A} \left\{ \frac{p^2}{4}(\mu^2 - 1)B - 4q^2(1-\nu^2) \frac{C^2}{B} \right\} d\phi^2, \quad (4.4.10)$$

where

$$A = \{p^2(\mu^2 - 1)^2 + q^2(1 - \nu^2)^2\}^2 - 4p^2q^2(\mu^2 - 1)(1 - \nu^2)(\mu^2 - \nu^2)^2, \quad (4.4.11)$$

$$B = (p^2\mu^4 + q^2\nu^4 - 1 + 2p\mu^3 - 2p\mu)^2 + 4q^2\nu^2(p\mu^3 - p\mu\nu^2 + 1 - \nu^2)^2, \quad (4.4.12)$$

and

$$C = q^2(1 + p\mu)(1 - \nu^2)^3 - p^2(\mu^2 - 1)(1 - \nu^2)(p\mu^3 + 3\mu^2 + 3p\mu + 1) - 2p^2\mu(\mu^2 - 1)^2(p\mu^2 + 2\mu + p). \quad (4.4.13)$$

The metric form defined in (4.4.10) is known as *Tomimatsu-Sato metric*.

4.4.1 Batic's recent transformation

With $\mu = \cosh x$ and $\nu = \cos y$ where $x \geq 0$ and $0 \leq y \leq \pi$ are the conventional definitions of prolate spheroidal coordinates (x, y, ϕ) , [Batic \[2023\]](#) recently transformed (4.4.10) into the form

$$ds^2 = \frac{A}{B} dt^2 - 4mq \sin^2 y \frac{C}{B} dt d\phi - \frac{m^2 B}{4p^2(\cosh^2 x - \cos^2 y)^3} (dx^2 + dy^2) - \frac{m^2 \sin^2 y}{4AB} (p^2 B^2 \sinh^2 x - 16q^2 C^2 \sin^2 y) d\phi^2, \quad (4.4.14)$$

where

$$A = (p^2 \sinh^4 x + q^2 \sin^4 y)^2 - 4p^2q^2 \sinh^2 x \sin^2 y (\cosh^2 x - \cos^2 y)^2, \quad (4.4.15)$$

$$B = (q^2 \cos^4 y + p^2 \cosh^4 x + 2p \cosh x \sinh^2 x - 1)^2 + 4q^2 \cos^2 y \times (p \cosh^3 x - p \cosh x \cos^2 y \sin^2 y)^2, \quad (4.4.16)$$

and

$$C = q^2 \sin^6 y (1 + p \cosh x) - p^2 \sinh^2 x \sin^2 y (p \cosh^3 x + 3 \cosh^2 x + 3p \cosh x + 1) - 2p^2 \cosh x \sinh^4 x (p \cosh^2 x + 2 \cosh x + p). \quad (4.4.17)$$

For $\delta > 0$, with the [Yamazaki \[1977\]](#) transformation in (r, θ) co-ordinates, such that

$$r = \frac{mp}{\delta} \mu + m, \quad \cos \theta = \nu, \quad (4.4.18)$$

in relation to the cylindrical co-ordinates (ϱ, z) , [Batic \[2023\]](#) expressed as

$$\varrho = \sqrt{(r-m)^2 - \left(\frac{mp}{\delta}\right)^2} \sin \theta, \quad z = (r-m) \cos \theta. \quad (4.4.19)$$

Since the deformation parameter, $\delta = 2$ represents the *T-S solution*, so that writing the co-ordinates (4.4.1) by

$$\begin{aligned} \varrho &= \frac{mp}{2} \sqrt{(\mu^2 - 1)(1 - \nu^2)} = \sqrt{\Delta} \sin \theta, \\ z &= \frac{mp}{2} \mu\nu = (r-m) \cos \theta, \quad \Delta \equiv (r-m)^2 - \frac{m^2 p^2}{4}, \end{aligned} \quad (4.4.20)$$

[Batic \[2023\]](#) obtained the transformation of prolate spheroidal co-ordinates in terms of the [Boyer and Lindquist \[1967\]](#) co-ordinates as

$$\begin{aligned} \mu &= \frac{\sqrt{R_+} + \sqrt{R_-}}{mp}, \quad \nu = \frac{(r-m) \cos \theta}{\sqrt{R_+} + \sqrt{R_-}}, \\ R_{\pm} &= \left(r - m \pm \frac{mp}{2} \cos \theta\right)^2. \end{aligned} \quad (4.4.21)$$

By considering the [Yamazaki \[1977\]](#) transformation (4.4.18) for $\delta = 2$, i.e,

$$\mu = \frac{2}{mp}(r-m), \quad \nu = \cos \theta, \quad (4.4.22)$$

the *T-S metric (line element)* (4.4.10) in Boyer-Lindquist co-ordinates obtained by [Batic \[2023\]](#) as

$$ds^2 = \frac{A}{B} dt^2 - 4mq \frac{C}{B} \sin^2 \theta dt d\phi - \sigma_1 \left(\frac{dr^2}{\Delta} + d\theta^2 \right) - \sigma_2 \sin^2 \theta d\phi^2, \quad (4.4.23)$$

with

$$\sigma_1 = \frac{m^8 p^4 B}{256 \left[(r-m)^2 - \frac{m^2 p^2}{4} \cos^2 \theta \right]^3}, \quad \sigma_2 = \frac{1}{A} \left(B\Delta - 4m^2 q^2 \frac{C^2}{B} \sin^2 \theta \right), \quad (4.4.24)$$

and A, B and C , given by (4.4.11), (4.4.12) and (4.4.13), respectively.

4.5 Bronnikov-Santos-Wang cylindrical systems

Recently [Bronnikov et al. \[2020\]](#) tried to study the general form of metric for the vacuum Einstein's field equations, that describes the rotating and non-rotating cylindrically symmetric spacetimes containing Gravitational Waves.

When sources that produce gravitational fields are removed from spacetime, curvature results. In this vacuum case, which is represented by Einstein's field equations $R_{\alpha\beta} = 0$, spacetime is flat and given by the metric $\eta_{\alpha\beta}$, also known as the Minkowski metric

$$ds^2 = \eta_{\alpha\beta} dx^\alpha dx^\beta = dt^2 - dx^2 - dy^2 - dz^2, \quad (4.5.1)$$

where t is the time coordinate and x, y , and z are Cartesian coordinates. The metric that results from

$$g_{\alpha\beta} = \eta_{\alpha\beta} + f_{\alpha\beta}, \quad (4.5.2)$$

where $f_{\alpha\beta}$ is a minor divergence from the Minkowski spacetime, leads to the Newtonian limit, which is what one would anticipate from Einstein's field equations.

If H represents the Newtonian potential and in the Newtonian approximation, from the spherically symmetric vacuum [Schwarzschild \[1916\]](#) solution (2.2.10), one has

$$g_{00} = 1 + 2H \quad (4.5.3)$$

so that

$$H = -\frac{m}{r}. \quad (4.5.4)$$

The cylindrically symmetric vacuum [Levi-Civita \[1917\]](#) solution that [Bronnikov et al. \[2020\]](#) considered by

$$ds^2 = \varrho^{4\sigma} dt^2 - \varrho^{4\sigma(2\sigma-1)} \left(d\varrho^2 + \frac{1}{a_x} dx^2 \right) - \frac{1}{a_y} \varrho^{2(1-2\sigma)} dy^2, \quad (4.5.5)$$

where σ, a_x and a_y are constants, and $0 \leq \varrho < \infty$ is the radial and $-\infty < t < +\infty$ the time co-ordinates. The characteristics of the coordinates x and y , which are currently unknown, rely on how the metric coefficients behave. A scale transformation can remove either a_x or a_y , depending on how the coordinates x and y behave. This leaves the metric with just two independent factors. By applying the transformation of radius ϱ into a proper length radial co-ordinate r by

$$\varrho^{2\sigma(2\sigma-1)} d\varrho = dr, \quad (4.5.6)$$

so that

$$\varrho = R^{\frac{1}{\Lambda}}, \quad R = \Lambda r, \quad \Lambda \equiv 4\sigma^2 - 2\sigma + 1, \quad (4.5.7)$$

for which the general Levi-Civita metric of (4.5.5) that [Bronnikov et al.](#) obtained by

$$ds^2 = R^{\frac{4\sigma}{\Lambda}} dt^2 - dr^2 - \frac{1}{a_x} R^{\frac{4\sigma(2\sigma-1)}{\Lambda}} dx^2 - \frac{1}{a_y} R^{\frac{2(1-2\sigma)}{\Lambda}} dy^2. \quad (4.5.8)$$

Considering the parameter $0 < \sigma < \frac{1}{2}$ and by rescaling z , if one interprets x as the axial co-ordinate $-\infty < z < \infty$ with $a_x = 1$ and y as the angular co-ordinate ϕ , then the metric (4.5.8) becomes

$$ds^2 = R^{\frac{4\sigma}{\Lambda}} dt^2 - dr^2 - R^{-\frac{4\sigma(1-2\sigma)}{\Lambda}} dz^2 - \frac{1}{a} R^{\frac{2(1-2\sigma)}{\Lambda}} d\phi^2, \quad (4.5.9)$$

where a_y is replaced by a . Similarly for $\frac{1}{2} < \sigma < \infty$, if one interprets x as the angular co-ordinate ϕ and again by rescaling z from y as the axial co-ordinate $-\infty < z < \infty$ with $a_y = 1$, then the metric (4.5.8) becomes

$$ds^2 = R^{\frac{4\sigma}{\Lambda}} dt^2 - dr^2 - R^{-\frac{2\sigma(2\sigma-1)}{\Lambda}} dz^2 - \frac{1}{a} R^{\frac{4\sigma(2\sigma-1)}{\Lambda}} d\phi^2, \quad (4.5.10)$$

where a_x is replaced by a .

For the canonical form of [Weyl \[1917\]](#) metric

$$ds^2 = e^{2\psi} dt^2 - e^{-2\psi} \{e^{2\lambda}(d\varrho^2 + dz^2) + \varrho^2 d\phi^2\}, \quad (4.5.11)$$

the solution of the field equations consisting the functions $\psi(\varrho, z)$ and $\lambda(\varrho, z)$ as

$$\psi_{,\varrho\varrho} + \frac{1}{\varrho}\psi_{,\varrho} + \psi_{,zz} = 0, \quad (4.5.12)$$

and

$$\lambda_{,\varrho} = \varrho(\psi_{,\varrho}^2 - \psi_{,z}^2), \quad \lambda_{,z} = 2\varrho\psi_{,\varrho}\psi_{,z} \quad (4.5.13)$$

where the comma stands for partial derivatives; that [Bronnikov et al. \[2020\]](#) obtain

$$e^{2\psi} = \left(\frac{R_+ + R_- - 2m}{R_+ + R_- + 2m} \right)^\varepsilon, \quad (4.5.14)$$

$$e^{2\lambda} = \left[\frac{(R_+ + R_-)^2 - 4m^2}{4R_+R_-} \right]^{\varepsilon^2}, \quad (4.5.15)$$

where

$$R_\pm^2 = \varrho^2 + (z \pm m)^2, \quad (4.5.16)$$

and ε and m are two integration constants. Immediately, one may derive

$$H = \varepsilon \ln \left(\frac{R_+ + R_- - m}{R_+ + R_- + m} \right) \quad (4.5.17)$$

which is a potential owing to a line segment of length $2m$ and mass per unit length $\frac{\varepsilon}{2}$ symmetrically distributed along the z -axis, by computing its Newtonian potential $g_{00} = e^{2H}$.

By taking the transformation of [Erez and Rosen \[1959\]](#) co-ordinates with the consideration of (4.5.16), defined by

$$\begin{aligned} \varrho &= \sqrt{\hat{\beta}} \sin^2 \theta, & \hat{\beta} &\equiv r^2 - 2mr, \\ z &= (r - m) \cos \theta, \end{aligned} \quad (4.5.18)$$

in the metric (4.5.11) corresponding to the solutions (4.5.14) and (4.5.15), the [Esposito and Witten \[1975\]](#) metric form one obtains

$$ds^2 = \left(1 - \frac{2m}{r}\right)^\varepsilon - \left(1 - \frac{2m}{r}\right)^{-\varepsilon} \left[\left(\frac{\hat{\beta}}{\hat{\Sigma}} \right)^{\varepsilon^2-1} dr^2 + \frac{(\hat{\beta})^{\varepsilon^2}}{(\hat{\Sigma})^{\varepsilon^2-1}} d\theta^2 + \hat{\beta} \sin^2 \theta d\phi^2 \right], \quad (4.5.19)$$

where $\hat{\beta}$ is defined in (4.5.18) and

$$\hat{\Sigma} \equiv \hat{\beta} + m^2 \sin^2 \theta. \quad (4.5.20)$$

It is now simple to verify that the metric (4.5.19) reduces to the [Schwarzschild \[1916\]](#) metric (2.2.10) when $\varepsilon = 1$.

Chapter 5

Metric Solutions by Modern Theoretic Method

5.1 Some Spheroidal space-time metrics

5.1.1 Vaidya & Tikekar spheroidal space-time

[Vaidya and Tikekar \[1982\]](#) explored the gravitational significance of space-times that have hypersurfaces $t = \text{constant}$ as 3-spheroids. Static models of the gravitational field inside superdense condensations of matter, such as white dwarfs and neutron stars, may be created using these 3-spheroidal space-times. They presented the 3-spheroidal space-time metric solutions for Einstein's gravitational field, which immerses from the metric of the four-dimensional flat space. It is noted that the central symmetry exists in spheroidal 3-space.

The 4-dimensional Euclidean flat space with metric is

$$d\sigma^2 = dx^2 + dy^2 + dz^2 + dw^2, \quad (5.1.1)$$

where the 3-spheroid immersed in this 4-dimensional flat space will be (in terms of Cartesian equation)

$$\frac{w^2}{b^2} + \frac{(x^2 + y^2 + z^2)}{R^2} = 1, \quad (5.1.2)$$

where b and R are two parameters. On the 3-spheroid, sections $x = \text{const}$, $y = \text{const}$, or $z = \text{const}$ show systems of confocal ellipsoids, where as sections $w = \text{const}$ are concentric spheres.

Consider [Vaidya and Tikekar \[1982\]](#)'s parametrization

$$\begin{aligned} x &= R \sin \lambda \sin \alpha \cos \beta \\ y &= R \sin \lambda \sin \alpha \sin \beta \\ z &= R \sin \lambda \cos \alpha \\ w &= b \cos \lambda, \end{aligned} \quad (5.1.3)$$

one can obtain the 3-spheroidal metric on the 3-space as

$$d\sigma^2 = (R^2 \cos^2 \lambda + b^2 \sin^2 \lambda) d\lambda^2 + R^2 \sin^2 \lambda (d\alpha^2 + \sin^2 \alpha d\beta^2). \quad (5.1.4)$$

If one introduces the space variable r by

$$r = R \sin \lambda,$$

the spatial metric (5.1.4) becomes

$$d\sigma^2 = \left\{ 1 - K \left(\frac{r^2}{R^2} \right) \right\} \left\{ 1 - \left(\frac{r^2}{R^2} \right) \right\}^{-1} dr^2 + r^2 (d\alpha^2 + \sin^2 \alpha d\beta^2), \quad (5.1.5)$$

where

$$K = 1 - \frac{b^2}{R^2}. \quad (5.1.6)$$

When $K = 0$ (i.e, $b = R$) occurs, the spheroidal 3-space turns spherical, and when $K = 1$, the spheroidal 3-space degenerates into flat 3-space. Then the spheroidal space-time metric will be

$$ds^2 = e^v dt^2 - \left\{ 1 - K \left(\frac{r^2}{R^2} \right) \right\} \left\{ 1 - \left(\frac{r^2}{R^2} \right) \right\}^{-1} dr^2 - r^2 (d\alpha^2 + \sin^2 \alpha d\beta^2), \quad (5.1.7)$$

where v is a function of r only.

5.1.2 Oblate spheroidal metric by Zipoy

A common practice in physics is to tailor the coordinate system to the issue; nevertheless, only cartesian, cylindrical, or spherical coordinate systems are often utilised, with other possible coordinate systems being relatively unknown and occasionally hard to visualise.

For obtaining the *oblate spheroidal metric* solution of Einstein [1915]'s vacuum field equations, Zipoy [1966] started from the familiar and completely general static cylindrically symmetric Weyl [1917] type line element

$$ds^2 = e^{2\sigma} dt^2 - e^{2(\lambda-\sigma)} (dr^2 + dz^2) - r^2 e^{-2\sigma} d\phi^2, \quad (5.1.8)$$

where $\lambda = \lambda(r, z)$ and $\sigma = \sigma(r, z)$ are two functions to be found by solving Einstein's vacuum field equations.

If one considers the *oblate spheroidal co-ordinates* (defined in Morse and Feshbach [1946]) making up the relation between r and z to the new co-ordinates u and θ as

$$r = a \cosh u \cos \theta, \quad z = a \sinh u \sin \theta, \quad (5.1.9)$$

where a is a constant, then the line element (5.1.8) becomes

$$ds^2 = e^{2\sigma} dt^2 - a^2 e^{2(\lambda-\sigma)} (\sinh^2 u + \sin^2 \theta) (du^2 + d\theta^2) - a^2 e^{-2\sigma} \cosh^2 u \cos^2 \theta d\phi^2. \quad (5.1.10)$$

The following four equations are the result of reducing the vacuum field equations to this metric.

$$\sigma_{11} + \sigma_{22} + \sigma_1 \tanh u - \sigma_2 \tan \theta = 0, \quad (5.1.11)$$

$$\sigma_1^2 - \sigma_2^2 - \lambda_1 \tanh u - \lambda_2 \tan \theta = 0, \quad (5.1.12)$$

$$2\sigma_1\sigma_2 + \lambda_1 \tan \theta - \lambda_2 \tanh u = 0, \quad (5.1.13)$$

$$\lambda_{11} + \lambda_{22} + \sigma_1^2 + \sigma_2^2 = 0, \quad (5.1.14)$$

where the subscripts 1 and 2 denote the partial differentiation with respect to r and z , respectively. In these coordinates, equation (5.1.11) is essentially Laplace's equation.

If one substitutes the suitable form

$$\eta = \sinh u, \quad \xi = \sin \theta, \quad (5.1.15)$$

in (5.1.11), then it becomes

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial \eta} \left\{ (\eta^2 + 1) \frac{\partial \sigma}{\partial \eta} \right\} + \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi} \left\{ (1 - \xi^2) \frac{\partial \sigma}{\partial \xi} \right\} = 0. \quad (5.1.16)$$

By applying the separation of variables equation (5.1.16) can easily be solved and then one can obtain the value of σ . Also, if one takes the additional condition that λ goes to zero as η goes to infinity, then from (5.1.12) and (5.1.13) one may obtain the value of λ from the following integration formula

$$\lambda = \int_{+\infty}^{\eta} \frac{(1 - \xi^2) \{ (\eta^2 + 1) \sigma_{\eta}^2 - (1 - \xi^2) \sigma_{\xi}^2 \} - 2\xi \sigma_{\eta} \sigma_{\xi}}{\eta^2 + \xi^2} d\xi. \quad (5.1.17)$$

5.1.3 q-metric in Spheroidal co-ordinates

The cylindrical co-ordinate system (r, z, ϕ, t) is considered to be adapted to the source's symmetries in the sense that the exterior solutions found will hold true outside of a certain hypersurface ($r = \text{const}$), which is referred to as the (surface of the) source.

5.1.3.1 Voorhees transformation

While studying the static axially symmetric gravitational fields, Voorhees [1970] systematically established the metric solution in some spheroidal co-ordinate systems, which is known in modern theory as q-metric. The line element form which Voorhees [1970] started, is the canonical form of Weyl [1917] class line element, defined by

$$ds^2 = e^{2\psi} dt^2 - e^{-2\psi} [e^{2\gamma} (dr^2 + dz^2) + r^2 d\phi^2], \quad (5.1.18)$$

where ψ and γ are functions of r and z only, The field equations formulated from (5.1.18) shows that ψ is a solution of the Laplace equation, for which γ can be uniquely determined.

By defining the oblate spheroidal co-ordinates

$$\begin{aligned} r &= k(u^2 + 1)^{1/2} (1 - v^2)^{1/2}, \\ z &= kuv, \end{aligned} \quad (5.1.19)$$

Voorhees [1970] assumed that if ψ be the Newtonian potential of an oblate spheroidal homoloid such that

$$\psi = \left(\frac{m}{k}\right) \cot^{-1} u, \quad (5.1.20)$$

then the metric form (line element) would be

$$\begin{aligned} ds^2 &= - \exp\left(\frac{m}{k} \cot^{-1} u\right) dt^2 + k^2 \exp\left(\frac{-m}{k} \cot^{-1} u\right) \\ &\times \left[(u^2 + 1)(1 - v^2) d\phi^2 + (u^2 + v^2) \left(\frac{u^2 + v^2}{u^2 + 1}\right)^{(m/k)^2} \left(\frac{du^2}{u^2 + 1} + \frac{dv^2}{1 - v^2}\right) \right], \end{aligned} \quad (5.1.21)$$

which actually represents an oblate spheroid. This metric solution was firstly derived by Misra [1960].

Further, to obtain the connection in Weyl [1917] co-ordinates, Voorhees [1970] defined the prolate spheroidal co-ordinates as

$$\begin{aligned} r &= k(u^2 - 1)^{1/2} (1 - v^2)^{1/2} \\ z &= kuv, \end{aligned} \quad (5.1.22)$$

such that the solution may reduce to the Schwarzschild [1916] metric by the transformation

$$u = \frac{r}{m} - 1, \quad v = \cos \theta, \quad (5.1.23)$$

under the assumption of $k = m$ in (5.1.22) is a spherical co-ordinate system.

Let (x, y) be another prolate spheroidal system fitted to the source that one may suppose $\delta = \frac{m}{k}$, so that (u, v) be unique prolate spheroidal co-ordinate system for $\delta = 1$. Then the metric solution, which was obtained by Voorhees [1970], one has

$$\begin{aligned} ds^2 &= - \left(\frac{x-1}{x+1}\right)^\delta dt^2 + k^2 \left(\frac{x+1}{x-1}\right)^\delta \\ &\times \left[(x^2 - y^2) \left(\frac{x^2 - 1}{x^2 - y^2}\right)^{\delta^2} \left(\frac{dx^2}{x^2 - 1} + \frac{dy^2}{1 - y^2}\right) + (x^2 - 1)(1 - y^2) d\phi^2 \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (5.1.24)$$

The metric solution (5.1.24) can easily be deduced in spherical co-ordinates by substitution of

$$\begin{aligned} x &= \frac{\delta}{\sqrt{2}} \left\{ u^2 + v^2 + \frac{1 - \delta^2}{\sqrt{2}} + \left[\left(u^2 + v^2 + \frac{1 - \delta^2}{\delta^2} \right)^2 - \frac{4u^2v^2}{\delta^2} \right]^{1/2} \right\}^{1/2} \\ y &= \frac{\delta}{\sqrt{2}} \left\{ u^2 + v^2 + \frac{1 - \delta^2}{\sqrt{2}} - \left[\left(u^2 + v^2 + \frac{1 - \delta^2}{\delta^2} \right)^2 - \frac{4u^2v^2}{\delta^2} \right]^{1/2} \right\}^{1/2}, \end{aligned} \quad (5.1.25)$$

and then (5.1.23).

5.1.3.2 Quevedo's formulation

Using a series method, for finding the solution of two-dimensional Laplace equation for ψ , which is one of the field equation for Weyl [1917] metric, Quevedo [1989] obtained the expression

$$\psi = \frac{1}{2} \ln \frac{r_+ + r_- - 2m}{r_+ + r_- + 2m}, \quad r_{\pm}^2 = r^2 + (z \pm m)^2, \quad (5.1.26)$$

where m is the mass of the source of the system. One can easily obtain the metric solution (5.1.24) from (5.1.18) through the substitution of Erez and Rosen [1959] prolate spheroidal co-ordinates (t, x, y, ϕ) in (5.1.26) as

$$x = \frac{r_+ + r_-}{2m}, \quad y = \frac{r_+ - r_-}{2m}, \quad x \geq 1, \quad -1 \leq y \leq 1. \quad (5.1.27)$$

Later, for the field equations of the metric solution (5.1.18) defined by

$$\begin{aligned} \psi_{rr} + \psi_{zz} + \frac{\psi_r}{r} &= 0, \\ \gamma_r &= r(\psi_r^2 - \psi_z^2), \\ \gamma_z &= 2r\psi_r\psi_z, \end{aligned} \quad (5.1.28)$$

Quevedo [2011] observed that for a real constant parameter δ , the Zipoy [1966]-Voorhees [1970] (ZV) transformation $\psi \rightarrow \delta\psi$ and $\gamma \rightarrow \delta^2\psi$ shows invariant. However, in addition to this, by letting $\delta = 1 + q$ in (5.1.24) in the sense of the transformation (5.1.23), the metric in spherical co-ordinate that Quevedo [2011] and Faraji [2022] obtained as

$$\begin{aligned} ds^2 &= \left(1 - \frac{2m}{r} \right)^{1+q} dt^2 - \left(1 - \frac{2m}{r} \right)^{-q} \\ &\times \left[\left(1 + \frac{m^2 \sin^2 \theta}{r^2 - 2mr} \right)^{-q(2+q)} \left(\frac{dr^2}{1 - \frac{2m}{r}} + r^2 d\theta^2 \right) + r^2 \sin^2 \theta d\phi^2 \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (5.1.29)$$

For all values of $q \rightarrow 0$, this axially symmetric solution reduces to the Schwarzschild [1916] metric with spherical symmetry. Also, it is evident that at $r = 0$, this metric exhibits a central curvature singularity and an additional singularity appears at $r = 2m$.

5.1.3.3 Generalized q-metric by Faraji

Using the parameter $\delta = 1 + q$ and $k = M(1 + q)$, considered by [Quevedo \[2011\]](#), the metric form (5.1.24) can be rewritten as (see [Erez and Rosen \[1959\]](#))

$$ds^2 = - \left(\frac{x-1}{x+1} \right)^{(1+q)} dt^2 + M^2(x^2-1) \left(\frac{x+1}{x-1} \right)^{(1+q)} \times \left[\left(\frac{x^2-1}{x^2-y^2} \right)^{q(2+q)} \left(\frac{dx^2}{x^2-1} + \frac{dy^2}{1-y^2} \right) + (1-y^2) d\phi^2 \right], \quad (5.1.30)$$

where $t \in (-\infty, +\infty)$, $x \in (1, +\infty)$, $y \in [-1, 1]$, and $0 \leq \phi < 2\pi$. This metric is commonly known as *q-metric*.

Recently, [Faraji \[2022\]](#) has generalized the q-metric (5.1.30). Considering the [Erez and Rosen \[1959\]](#) prolate co-ordinates (t, x, y, ϕ) given in (5.1.27), he transformed the field equation (5.1.28) by

$$[(x^2-1)\psi_x]_x + [(1-y^2)\psi_y]_y = 0, \quad (5.1.31)$$

$$\gamma_x = \frac{1-y^2}{x^2-y^2} [x(x^2-1)\psi_x^2 - x(1-y^2)\psi_y^2 - 2y(x^2-1)\psi_x\psi_y], \quad (5.1.32)$$

$$\gamma_y = \frac{1-y^2}{x^2-y^2} [y(x^2-1)\psi_x^2 - y(1-y^2)\psi_y^2 + 2x(1-y^2)\psi_x\psi_y], \quad (5.1.33)$$

where the suffix represents the partial derivatives. By making use of the separation of variables in (5.1.31) and followed by solving Legendre's equation (see [Abramowitz \[1965\]](#)), the solution ψ one may obtain

$$\psi = \psi_q + \hat{\psi}, \quad (5.1.34)$$

where

$$\psi_q = \frac{(1+q)}{2} \ln \left(\frac{x-1}{x+1} \right)$$

is defined as the ψ -field function for q-metric. Again corresponding to this potential ψ , explicitly, the field function γ from (5.1.32) and (5.1.33), one obtains

$$\gamma = \gamma_q + \hat{\gamma}, \quad (5.1.35)$$

where

$$\gamma_q = \frac{(1+q)^2}{2} \ln \left(\frac{x^2-1}{x^2-y^2} \right)$$

is defined as the γ -field function for q-metric. Here $\hat{\psi}$ and $\hat{\gamma}$ are to be obtained as the series representations containing Legendre polynomials. The Schwarzschild fields are covered under the restrictions $\hat{\psi} = 0$, $\hat{\gamma} = 0$, and $q = 0$, as may be readily verified. Then the generalized q-metric defined by [Faraji \[2022\]](#) is

$$ds^2 = - \left(\frac{x-1}{x+1} \right)^{(1+q)} e^{2\hat{\psi}} dt^2 + M^2(x^2-1) e^{-2\hat{\psi}} \left(\frac{x+1}{x-1} \right)^{(1+q)} \times \left[\left(\frac{x^2-1}{x^2-y^2} \right)^{q(2+q)} e^{2\hat{\gamma}} \left(\frac{dx^2}{x^2-1} + \frac{dy^2}{1-y^2} \right) + (1-y^2) d\phi^2 \right]. \quad (5.1.36)$$

5.1.4 Doran's Spheroidal Kerr metric

In Cartesian-type co-ordinates (t, x, y, z) , the new form of the [Kerr \[1963\]](#) solution that [Doran \[2000\]](#) considered as

$$ds^2 = \eta_{ij} dx^i dx^j - \left(\frac{2\varpi}{\rho} a_i \epsilon_j + \alpha^2 \epsilon_i \epsilon_j \right) dx^i dx^j, \quad (5.1.37)$$

where η_{ij} is the Minkowski metric,

$$\begin{aligned} \varpi &= \frac{\sqrt{2mr}}{\rho} \\ \rho^2 &= r^2 + \frac{a^2 z^2}{r^2}, \end{aligned} \quad (5.1.38)$$

and a and m are constants. Given implicitly by

$$r^4 - r^2(x^2 + y^2 + z^2 - a^2) - a^2 z^2 = 0, \quad (5.1.39)$$

one limits the function r to $0 < r < \infty$, where $r = 0$ describes the disk $z = 0$, $x^2 + y^2 \leq a^2$. The two vectors in the metric (5.1.37) are defined by

$$\epsilon_i = \left(1, \frac{ay}{a^2 + r^2}, \frac{-ax}{a^2 + r^2}, 0 \right), \quad (5.1.40)$$

and

$$a_i = \sqrt{a^2 + r^2} \left(0, \frac{rx}{a^2 + r^2}, \frac{ry}{a^2 + r^2}, \frac{z}{r} \right). \quad (5.1.41)$$

Considering the [Doran \[2000\]](#)'s oblate spheroidal co-ordinates (r, θ, ϕ) defined by

$$\cos \theta = \frac{z}{r}, \quad \tan \phi = \frac{y}{x}, \quad \text{where } 0 \leq \theta \leq \pi, \quad 0 \leq \phi < 2\pi, \quad (5.1.42)$$

so that ρ takes the form defined in (4.2.4) corresponding to (5.1.38) as

$$\rho^2 = r^2 + a^2 \cos^2 \theta,$$

into the metric (5.1.37) yields

$$ds^2 = dt^2 - \left(\frac{\rho}{\sqrt{r^2 + a^2}} dr + \varpi(dt - a \sin^2 \theta d\phi) \right)^2 - \rho^2 d\theta^2 - (r^2 + a^2) \sin^2 \theta d\phi^2. \quad (5.1.43)$$

As $r \neq \sqrt{(x^2 + y^2 + z^2)}$, it clearly shows that for $m = 0$ the cartesian co-ordinates reduce to the oblate spheroidal co-ordinates under the *Doran's spheroidal co-ordinate transformation* (5.1.42) and not spherical polar co-ordinates.

5.2 Throne-Peters Toroidal spacetimes

Let b represents the radius of two disks where a uniform line singularity (source) occurs on the common axis between the two disks, where the normal derivative of the generating potential disappears, and where the disks are separated by a distance of $2a$.

In cylindrical co-ordinates the axially symmetric static Weyl [1917] class metric that Thorne [1975] and Peters [1979] considered, is defined in (4.5.11), where ψ is the generating potential and λ can be obtained by integration once ψ is known. Selecting various singular sources (point, line, and surface sources) for ψ in the backdrop space yields various solutions for the metric (4.5.11). When the sources are limited to a small area inside the background space, ψ and λ will converge to constants as $(\varrho^2 + z^2)^{1/2} \rightarrow \infty$. These constants can be selected to zero without compromising generality, resulting in an asymptotically Minkowskiian physical spacetime.

Toroidal solutions were generated more easily by Thorne [1975] and Peters [1979] choosing the source of ψ in the background space, which is a ring singularity around the axis of symmetry, so that at $[(\varrho - b)^2 + z^2]^{1/2} \ll b$ (near singularity), the generating potential ψ takes the form by

$$\psi = \ln [(\varrho - b)^2 + z^2]^{1/2} \times \text{const.} \quad (5.2.1)$$

In order to circumvent the complications associated with the physical metric in the locally cylindrical form close to the singularity, Thorne [1975] took into account the ring source of ψ at $\varrho = b, z = 0$.

For the new toroidal solution at $|z| < a, \varrho \ll \max(a, b)$ near singularity, after solving the potentials ψ and λ , Thorne [1975] obtained

$$\begin{aligned} \psi &= \frac{M}{a} \ln \varrho + \psi_0, \\ \lambda &= \left(\frac{M}{a}\right)^2 \ln \varrho + \lambda_0, \end{aligned} \quad (5.2.2)$$

where ψ_0 and λ_0 are constants and M is the total gravitational mass-energy. It is evident that ψ vanishes at spatial infinity

$$\psi = -\frac{M}{r} \quad \text{as} \quad r = (\varrho^2 + z^2)^{1/2} \rightarrow \infty, \quad (5.2.3)$$

and λ vanishes at spatial infinity as well.

On the substitution of (5.2.2) into the Weyl class metric (4.5.11), the toroidal spacetime metric that Thorne [1975] obtained by

$$ds^2 = e^{2\psi_0} \varrho^{2M/a} dt^2 - e^{-2\psi_0} \left\{ e^{2\lambda_0} \varrho^{2(\frac{M}{a})(\frac{M}{a}-1)} (d\varrho^2 + dz^2) + \varrho^{(2-\frac{2M}{a})} d\phi^2 \right\}, \quad (5.2.4)$$

where z is a periodic coordinate in this spacetime area that surrounds the singularity $-a \leq z \leq +a$, and ϕ is a "longitudinal coordinate" that stretches along the singularity. However, [Peters \[1979\]](#) took the special case $\frac{M}{a} = 1$, for which at a general singularity near $\varrho = 0$, the [Thorne \[1975\]](#)'s metric (5.2.4) becomes

$$ds^2 = e^{2\psi_0} \varrho^2 dt^2 - e^{-2\psi_0} \{e^{2\lambda_0} (d\varrho^2 + dz^2) + d\phi^2\}. \quad (5.2.5)$$

Further introducing the co-ordinates u and v , defined by

$$u = \alpha \varrho \cosh \varphi t, \quad v = \alpha \varrho \sinh \varphi t, \quad (5.2.6)$$

into the metric (5.2.4), [Peters \[1979\]](#) obtained as

$$ds^2 = dv^2 - du^2 - e^{-2\psi_0} [e^{2\lambda_0} dz^2 + d\phi^2], \quad (5.2.7)$$

where $\alpha = e^{\lambda_0 - \psi_0}$, $\varphi = e^{2\psi_0 - \lambda_0}$ and $u^2 - v^2 = \alpha^2 \varrho^2$ having the locus point at $\varrho = 0$.

5.3 ε -metric and Quasi-Hyperbolicity

The [Schwarzschild \[1916\]](#) solution is one of the unique static, spherically symmetric, asymptotically flat solution to Einstein's gravitational field equations for empty space. If R be the Schwarzschild radius and m be the total Newtonian mass of the field then for $R > 2m$ in polar co-ordinates having the metric signature form $(-, +, +, +)$, the line element we have

$$ds^2 = - \left(1 - \frac{2m}{R}\right) dt^2 + \frac{dR^2}{\left(1 - \frac{2m}{R}\right)} + R^2 d\Omega^2 \quad (5.3.1)$$

$$d\Omega^2 = d\theta^2 + \sin^2 \theta d\phi^2,$$

where t is the time co-ordinate and this static solution describes a space with a positive Gaussian curvature using a (θ, ϕ) curved 2-surface.

Coordinate transformations that provide acceptable solutions of the Einstein equations for vacuum with an unchanging signature throughout the whole resulting space-time are possible as there is no algebraic singularity at the horizon ($R = 2m$). Although mathematically but not depicting a physical solution, for $R < 2m$, with the change of metric signature $(+, -, +, +)$, [Herrera and Witten \[2018\]](#) presented an inside static symmetric solution in the sense of Schwarzschild.

[Herrera and Witten \[2018\]](#) made the observation that the $\theta - \phi$ sub-manifolds have a hyperbolic symmetry in the interior and a spherical symmetry on the exterior via insisting on a static solution everywhere that necessitates a drastically different interpretation of the relevance of the horizon. The transformation $d\Omega^2 \rightarrow -d\Omega^2$ is necessary for this, and it naturally entails a detour over the complex plane.

Thus, for $R < 2m$, Herrera & Witten obtains

$$\begin{aligned} ds^2 &= \left(\frac{2m}{R} - 1 \right) dt^2 - \frac{dR^2}{\left(\frac{2m}{R} - 1 \right)} - R^2 d\Omega^2 \\ d\Omega^2 &= d\theta^2 + \sinh^2 \theta d\phi^2, \end{aligned} \quad (5.3.2)$$

while accepting the hyperbolic symmetry, this is also a static solution where the (θ, ϕ) space describes a positive Gaussian curvature with the time coordinate t .

Since ε is a constant parameter in [Erez and Rosen \[1959\]](#) coordinates, (4.5.19) defines the line element for the ε -metric containing (4.5.18) and (4.5.20) (see [Esposito and Witten \[1975\]](#), [Bronnikov et al. \[2020\]](#)). Given the equation

$$M = \varepsilon m, \quad Q = \varepsilon (1 - \varepsilon^2) \frac{m^3}{3}, \quad (5.3.3)$$

the mass (monopole) M and quadrupole moment Q of the solution are obtained, suggesting that the source will be oblate (prolate) for $\varepsilon > 1$ ($\varepsilon < 1$). By using the above discussed cause for hyperbolicity and singularity of the field, the hyperbolic version of the line element (4.5.19) that [Herrera et al. \[2023\]](#) obtained recently as

$$ds^2 = \left(\frac{2m}{r} - 1 \right)^\varepsilon - \left(\frac{2m}{r} - 1 \right)^{-\varepsilon} \left[\left(\frac{\hat{\beta}^*}{\hat{\Sigma}^*} \right)^{\varepsilon^2 - 1} dr^2 + \frac{(\hat{\beta}^*)^{\varepsilon^2}}{(\hat{\Sigma}^*)^{\varepsilon^2 - 1}} d\theta^2 + \hat{\beta}^* \sinh^2 \theta d\phi^2 \right], \quad (5.3.4)$$

where

$$\hat{\beta}^* = 2mr - r^2, \quad \text{and} \quad \hat{\Sigma}^* = \hat{\beta}^* + m^2 \sinh^2 \theta. \quad (5.3.5)$$

This makes it simple to verify that $\varepsilon = 1$ corresponds to the line element (5.3.2) and that (5.3.4) is a solution to the vacuum Einstein equations. But in this instance, since the curvature invariants are singular on that surface (in line with the [Israel \[1967\]](#) Theorem expectations), the surface $r = 2m$ represents a naked singularity if $\varepsilon \neq 1$.

5.4 Kerr Extremal Throat Geometry

Since [Kerr \[1963\]](#) metric defines the static axially symmetric solution of the [Einstein \[1915\]](#)'s field equations for a vacuum case, in [Boyer and Lindquist \[1967\]](#) co-ordinates one writes

$$ds^2 = \rho^2 \left(\frac{d\bar{r}^2}{\beta} + d\bar{\theta}^2 \right) + \beta \sin^2 \bar{\theta} e^{-2\kappa} (d\bar{\phi} - \omega d\bar{t})^2 - e^{2\kappa} d\bar{t}^2, \quad (5.4.1)$$

where ρ and β are given in (4.2.4) and (4.2.8), respectively, and

$$e^{2\kappa} = \frac{\beta \rho^2}{(\bar{r}^2 + a^2)^2 - \beta a^2 \sin^2 \bar{\theta}}, \quad \omega = \frac{2m \bar{r} a}{\beta \rho^2} e^{2\kappa}. \quad (5.4.2)$$

$J = ma$, which one shall assume to be positive, is the angular momentum, ω is the angular velocity of the horizon, and m is the total mass. [Bardeen and Horowitz \[1999\]](#) observed that the *event horizon* for the metric form (5.4.1), at $\bar{r} = m$ corresponds to the extremal limit $a^2 = m^2$, so that $\beta = (\bar{r} - m)^2$, for which the area of the *extremal horizon* is

$$A = 8\pi m^2 = 8\pi J. \quad (5.4.3)$$

The spatial distance to the extremal horizon in a constant $\bar{t}$ surface is obviously infinite, as $g_{\bar{r}\bar{r}} = \frac{\rho^2}{\beta}$. Thus the black hole horizon one may find (see [Meinel \[2002\]](#))

$$\bar{r}_+ \equiv m + \sqrt{m^2 - a^2}, \quad (5.4.4)$$

so that for $a \leq m$ a black hole can be described by [Kerr \[1963\]](#) metric (5.4.1) and

$$\bar{r}_0(\bar{\theta}) \equiv m + \sqrt{m^2 - a^2 \cos^2 \bar{\theta}} \quad (5.4.5)$$

characterizes the boundary of the ‘*ergosphere*’.

By considering the [Bardeen and Horowitz \[1999\]](#) co-ordinate transformation

$$\bar{r} = m + \varsigma r, \quad \bar{\theta} = \theta, \quad \bar{t} = \frac{t}{\varsigma}, \quad \bar{\phi} = \phi + \frac{t}{2m\varsigma}, \quad (5.4.6)$$

in the limit $\varsigma \rightarrow 0$, that describes the *near-horizon* (throat) geometry, the metric (5.4.1) reduces to (see [Meinel \[2002\]](#))

$$ds^2 = m^2 (1 + \cos^2 \theta) \left(\frac{dr^2}{r^2} + d\theta^2 - \frac{r^2 dt^2}{4m^4} \right) + \frac{4m^2 \sin^2 \theta}{1 + \cos^2 \theta} \left(d\phi + \frac{r dt}{2m^2} \right)^2. \quad (5.4.7)$$

As a fully non-singular vacuum solution of Einstein’s equations, this spacetime is no longer asymptotically flat.

Further by setting $2m^2 = 1$ in (5.4.7), after the introduction of a new co-ordinate transformation

$$r = (1 + y^2)^{1/2} \cos \tau + y, \quad t = \frac{(1 + y^2)^{1/2} \sin \tau}{r}, \quad (5.4.8)$$

$$\phi = \varphi + \log \left| \frac{\cos \tau + y \sin \tau}{1 + (1 + y^2)^{1/2} \sin \tau} \right|,$$

for finding the extra global time translation symmetry, [Bardeen and Horowitz \[1999\]](#) obtains the throat metric as

$$ds^2 = \left(\frac{1 + \cos^2 \theta}{2} \right) \left(\frac{dy^2}{1 + y^2} + d\theta^2 - (1 + y^2) d\tau^2 \right) + \frac{2 \sin^2 \theta}{1 + \cos^2 \theta} (d\varphi + y d\tau)^2. \quad (5.4.9)$$

Again, upon the consideration of a new variable $x = \frac{1}{r}$ through multiplying by $\frac{1}{r^2}$ into (5.4.7), the metric that [Bardeen and Horowitz \[1999\]](#) obtains as

$$ds^2 = \left(\frac{1 + \cos^2 \theta}{2} \right) (dx^2 + x^2 d\theta^2 - dt^2) + \frac{2 \sin^2 \theta}{1 + \cos^2 \theta} (xd\phi + dt)^2, \quad (5.4.10)$$

where $2m^2 = 1$ and at $x = 0$ this conformal metric depicts the curvature singularity.

Chapter 6

Conclusion

This dissertation has systematically investigated the static symmetric solutions to Einstein's field equations, elucidating critical aspects of spacetime geometry and gravitational phenomena. Through rigorous mathematical analysis and a comprehensive review of the Schwarzschild metric and its various extensions, this work has significantly enhanced our understanding of these fundamental solutions in General Relativity.

The examination of coordinate transformations—encompassing Gullstrand-Painlevé, Eddington-Finkelstein, Lemaître, and Kruskal-Szekeres coordinates—offered profound insights into the manifold interpretations and applications of these solutions. These transformations are essential for revealing the underlying physics and facilitating the extension of these metrics to more intricate scenarios.

Advanced theoretical constructs, such as the Einstein-Rosen Bridge and Synge's tetrad formalism, were scrutinized, showcasing their substantial implications for modern theoretical physics. The study of isotropic extensions by Nariai and anisotropic extensions by Finkelstein illustrated the versatility and depth of Einstein's equations in modeling diverse astrophysical and cosmological phenomena.

In exploring axially symmetric solutions, this thesis provided an in-depth analysis of the Weyl, Lewis, and Kerr metrics, as well as the more complex Tomimatsu-Sato and Batic transformations. These analyses highlighted the rich spectrum of possible spacetime configurations, particularly in the context of rotating bodies and gravitational wave phenomena.

Investigations into spheroidal and toroidal spacetimes, including the spheroidal metrics by Vaidya & Tikekar and toroidal solutions by Thorne-Peters, demonstrated the varied morphologies that spacetime can adopt under different physical conditions. The Kerr extremal throat geometry, in particular, offered a compelling glimpse into the extremal limits of black hole solutions, pushing the boundaries of our theoretical understanding.

This comprehensive study significantly contributes to the field of theoretical physics, providing a foundational reference for future research endeavors. The findings presented herein not only enhance our understanding of static symmetric solutions but also pave the way for exploring more complex and dynamic solutions within the framework of General Relativity. By employing meticulous mathematical scrutiny and innovative theoretical methods, this thesis underscores the enduring relevance and profound implications of Einstein's field equations in the ongoing quest to unravel the mysteries of the universe.

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